

The Archaeology of Insurrection

An investigation into the subsistence behaviours of the
Batavia survivors

Ben Marwick

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Centre for Archaeology
Department of Anthropology
University of Western Australia

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CENTRE FOR ARCHAEOLOGY
The University of Western Australia

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Chapter One Introduction

Historical Background

In June 1629 the Dutch trading vessel *Batavia* wrecked on a reef in the northern group of islands at the Houtman Abrolhos, Western Australia. As the ship broke up, passengers, soldiers and crew were ferried to Beacon Island, a small desolate coral island with no fresh water. Three days later the ship's commander, Francisco Pelsaert, left with a small group to search for water, and to seek assistance from the Dutch colony in Java, located 1,700 km to the north. Pelsaert's journal provides some information on the events and movements of the survivors after the shipwreck. The journal suggests that about 230 people were left stranded for nearly four months until Pelsaert's return. While Pelsaert was away the survivors subsisted on salvaged food, and small amounts of native fauna and fish. Almost a month after the shipwreck a violent insurrection occurred.

According to historical documents, the mutineers moved the soldiers away from the *Batavia* wreck to West Wallabi Island, hoping the soldiers would perish. The mutineers planned to capture the rescue vessel and intended for the soldiers to die to eliminate any opposition. Although the soldiers did not have access to the shipwreck or salvaged food, they were able to subsist on the abundant native fauna on West Wallabi Island. Meanwhile, on Beacon Island and surrounding islands the mutineers murdered 125 passengers and crew and made several unsuccessful attempts (through bribery and pitched battles) to kill the soldiers and other people who had fled to West Wallabi Island. When Pelsaert returned on 17 September 1629, he captured the mutineers without resistance and trialed, tortured and executed the leaders (see figure 1.1 for a schematic overview of the activities and movements of the *Batavia* survivors on the Abrolhos Islands).

Figure 1.1
Schematic chart showing the course of events and movements of *Batavia* survivors on the Abrolhos Islands

Aims

The aims of this thesis are to investigate the how the two different groups from the *Batavia* survived the crises of shipwreck and mutiny through an analysis of archaeological faunal data and documentary sources. Two faunal assemblages were compared; one representing the survivors on Beacon Island and the other representing the survivors on West Wallabi Island. The documentary sources contain details on both groups, suggesting that the mutineers and other survivors on Beacon Island subsisted mainly on salvaged food and scarce native fauna, while the soldiers and other survivors on West Wallabi Island subsisted entirely on abundant native fauna. The crisis of shipwreck is defined as the transition from the relatively predicible social and subsistence conditions on board the *Batavia* to 'the difficult dynamics of individual or group isolation, and the necessities to salvage, adapt and survive in unfamiliar and potentially hostile environments' (Gibbs n.d.:1). In this context the crisis of mutiny is defined as the separation of the survivors into two hostile groups with different social organisations and potentially different subsistence resources.

Sources of data

There were two main bodies of data used in this study: archaeological faunal remains and historic descriptions. Archaeological data consists of the analysis of faunal material recovered from the *Batavia* survivors' camps on Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island. Faunal material examined in this study was recovered by the expeditions conducted in 1967 (led by Colin Jack-Hinton) and 1974 (led by Robert Bevacqua). The recovery of the faunal material is discussed in chapter three, and the analytical methods developed for the faunal material are discussed in chapter four. The research potential of the archaeological material was limited by the absence of details on recovery methods for the 1967 expedition. The limitations of the archaeological data are discussed throughout the study. Archaeological data from other sources, such as the Aquinas College expeditions of 1964 and 1965, and excavations on the *Batavia* shipwreck are included in the discussion of the results of the faunal analysis in chapter five. Taphonomy and site formation processes are discussed in chapter three as part of an attempt to identify natural and cultural transformations of the faunal remains and

understand how these transformations relate to the faunal remains of the *Batavia* survivors.

Documentary data on the *Batavia* survivors' subsistence behaviours are derived from Pelsaert's journal, the preacher's letter, the letters of two passengers and contemporary secondary sources (such as illustrations to published accounts of the wreck). The analysis of the documentary sources is discussed in chapter two.

Combining archaeological and documentary data

This investigation involved the combination of archaeological and historical data to create and test predictions regarding the survivors' subsistence behaviours. Archaeologists need to be cautious not to privilege textual records over archaeological findings (Feinman 1997). Uncritical approaches to the use of these data are typified by the one-way use of the documentary record to interpret the archaeological record that then fills gaps and adds detail to the documentary record (Leone and Potter 1988:11-12). An alternative approach has been influenced by Binford's concepts of ambiguity and middle-range theory. This approach attempts to be less biased by combining archaeological and historical data without privileging one over the other (Leone and Potter 1988).

Middle-range theory is an archaeological version of methodological uniformitarianism, consisting of a body of theories 'that permit the accurate conversion of statics [the material record] to statements about dynamics [the cultural past]' (Binford 1981:25; cf. Raab and Goodyear 1984; Shott 1998). Binford (1977; 1987) suggests the archaeological record can be interpreted through observations and knowledge of living cultural systems provided by ethnoarchaeological research. In Binford's approach, archaeological data and ethnographic data are treated as parallel and independent data sources. Points of disagreement between the archaeological and ethnographic data sources are called ambiguities, and used as the basis for a new set of questions about the archaeological and ethnographic records (Leone and Potter 1988:14).

In historical archaeology, Leone and others have appropriated Binford's middle-range theory as a method for combining archaeological and documentary data (Leone

1988; Leone and Potter 1988; Leone and Crosby 1987). In this approach documentary data takes the place of ethnoarchaeological data as a parallel and independent source of data about the past (Leone and Crosby 1987; Gibbs 1995:29). A framework of behaviours is derived from the documentary data and used to create expectations of the archaeological record and vice versa (Leone and Potter 1988:14; Potter 1992). Areas where the data deviates from expectations are called ambiguities, and are used as the basis for a new set of questions about the archaeological record and the documentary record.

The middle-range approach in historical archaeology has been criticised by Beaudry, Cook and Mrozowski (1991), who describe it as a justification for archaeologists to be suspicious of documents and emic sources by separating them from the artefacts. They encourage 'detailed construction of the historical and cultural context of artefact use through a critical reading of cultural texts' (Beaudry et al. 1991:153). According to Beaudry et al. (1991:160), the role of documentary records in the construction of historical context should be combined with its role in the generation of archaeological expectations described by Leone and Potter (1988). Although Beaudry et al. (1991) propose a more sophisticated approach, the methods they suggest are not substantially different from the middle-range approach (Gibbs 1995:30-31).

In this study an approach based on middle-range theory was used in combination with hermeneutic methods (Kosso 1991; Tschauer 1996). An important principle of hermeneutics is that the meaning of details (data) derives in part from its relationship to the whole (theory), and the whole is understood in terms of the details (Hodder 1986:150; 1999:32-33; Johnson and Olsen 1992). The hermeneutic circle or spiral is the dialectical process of interpreting and reinterpreting the data-theory relationship (Hodder 1991; Ricoeur 1971). The observation of data in this study was initially structured by a theory of the *Batavia* survivors' subsistence behaviours derived from documentary data. This approach is supported by Wylie's (1985:73) comment that 'observational experience is actively structured by the observer and acquires significance as evidence... only under theory-specific interpretation'. A subsistence theory derived from documentary sources was used in the development of predictions about faunal data. The predictions then became the basis of the framework for the archaeological analysis. Taphonomic data, site formation processes and documentary data were considered in the analysis and interpretation of the archaeological material. A continuous feedback between theory and data was attempted, as recommended by

Wylie (1989), Bernstein (1983) and Hodder (1986:18), and as the study progressed, new findings resulted in modifications of the theory of subsistence and interpretations of the archaeological and documentary data.

Discussion

In this study, the reconstruction of subsistence behaviours through documentary and archaeological data was expected to provide an understanding how people from the *Batavia* adapted and survived the events following the shipwreck. The process of adaptation is one of an 'alteration of a cultural system (either in its elements or the relation of the elements, or both) in response to change in its coupled environment and/or somatic systems' (Kirch 1980:108). Adaptive changes result from perceptions of the environment, including observations on social conditions and the individual's wellbeing (Kirch 1980:112). The *Batavia* survivors had to adapt to a dynamic change from a closed ship-bound community with dependable resources to a stressful shipwreck and mutiny in an unfamiliar area with unfamiliar resources. The subsistence behaviours of the *Batavia* survivors are one set of behaviours where the process of adaptation can be observed.

An individual from the seventeenth-century Netherlands travelling aboard the *Batavia* may have perceived two types of resources when shipwrecked on the Abrolhos Islands. One set of resources would be those carried by the ship and the other set the resources available in the surrounding local environment. The most familiar type to the *Batavia* passengers and crew was possibly the ship's stores of water, wine, bread and salted beef and pork. The second type of resources, including fish, birds, reptiles and exotic fauna, may have been familiar only to experienced sailors and people who had been previously shipwrecked. This study aimed to identify which (if any) of the two resource subsets dominated the subsistence resources of the *Batavia* survivors, and how the resources were related in the unique context of the *Batavia* mutiny. An understanding of the relationship between the two resource subsets may provide an indication of the degree of behavioural and psychological adaptation of the survivors to their situation.

In this thesis, because of the unique context of each group of survivors, the subsistence behaviours of the survivors on Beacon Island were compared to the

subsistence behaviours of the survivors on West Wallabi Island. There are several key elements to consider when comparing the two groups. These include; natural species diversity and density in the local island environment, access to resources from wreck, and social context and organisation.

Beacon Island has a very low species density and diversity, relative to West Wallabi Island, which has the highest in the Wallabi Group. The availability of native resources from the islands may have determined reliance on resources from the wreck. Proximity and access to the wreck may also have influenced the importance of resources from the wreck in the survivors' subsistence behaviours. The historical record suggests that the mutineers controlled access to the wreck from Beacon Island, with West Wallabi Island approximately five times further away from the wreck than Beacon Island. Based on the data in the documentary sources and information about the local environment, it was expected that the survivors on Beacon Island subsisted mainly on salvaged fauna, while those on West Wallabi Island subsisted mainly on native fauna.

The analysis food preparation and disposal was another avenue for investigating the survivors' adaptation to the post-shipwreck social and environmental conditions. The different groups may have prepared their food differently depending on the scarcity of the resources and whether food was shared. Where resources are scarce, effort might be made to maximise the dietary contribution of each animal, which might include breaking the bone to extract marrow, boiling it to make soup and eating less palatable parts. The archaeological expression of this kind of adaptation to scarce resources might include bone fracturing patterns and a high degree of bone fragmentation (Hodder 1979:449).

Butchering patterns were used in this study in an attempt to demonstrate differences in the distribution of available resources amongst each population. The extent that an animal is butchered may be proportional to how widely it is shared. Barrelled fauna and animals with no evidence of butchery may have been shared, although in context of the *Batavia* survivors this type of sharing is probably archaeologically undetectable. In this thesis it was proposed that the degree of resource sharing potentially reflected resource abundance and social organisation. An open egalitarian social system or a fair hierarchical system, as the documentary record describes the soldiers on West Wallabi Island, may share food across the population. A social system controlled by a selfish oligarchy, such as the mutineers on Beacon Island,

would be less likely to share limited resources beyond the ruling group. Hoarding and sharing food are means of actively defining social relations and are intentional symbolic constructions in the archaeological record (Gumerman 1997:109; Hodder 1986:6).

Summary

Inferences relating to the *Batavia* survivors' subsistence behaviours were based on the analysis of faunal remains and documentary sources. A reflexive approach was taken during the analysis of data. Initial analysis of documentary sources lead to the formation of the following predictions, which were investigated and modified during the analysis of faunal remains and further analysis of historical sources:

1. The group on Beacon Island subsisted mainly on salvaged fauna, while those on West Wallabi Island subsisted mainly on native fauna.
2. Patterns of food preparation were different for each group. The variables of resource scarcity and food-sharing behaviour influence patterns of food preparation.
3. The degree of resource sharing within each island's population reflects resource abundance, social organisation and the relationship between the two groups.

Chapter Two The *Batavia*: The Sources and the Story

Introduction

This chapter provides a discussion of the data contained in the historical sources describing the *Batavia* voyage and shipwreck. The documentary sources were specifically considered for data on the survivors' subsistence behaviours and how the crises affected these behaviours. In addition, the documentary sources were examined for information on the events that separated the survivors into two hostile groups. The records were also examined to determine how the division into two groups affected each group's access to victuals from the wreck and how the local environment of each group influenced subsistence behaviours. Events prior to the shipwreck (such as the incidents during the voyage) are included here because they are connected in causal ways to the behaviour of the survivors on the islands (Keat and Urry 1975:31; Flannery 1986:514).

Historical method

The written textual sources of data for the voyage and shipwreck include VOC (*Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie* or The United Dutch East India Company) records, the fleet commander's journal, a letter written by the *Batavia* predicant (preacher), two letters written by passengers and an illustrated novel published eighteen years after the wreck. The aim was to use the sources in the construction of a narrative that examines the survivors' subsistence behaviours during the crises of mutiny and division into two opposing groups.

Two important processes in examining historical documents are external criticism and internal criticism. External criticism is concerned with the authenticity of a document (Gottschalk 1958:118-138; Shafer 1980:127-148). This involves determining the author and date of the document and analysing the document for signs of forgery

or later restoration. According to Gottschalk (1958:122-138) and Shafer (1980:127-148), forgery and restoration can be detected by an anachronistic style, comparing the document to other pieces of evidence, and various physical approaches (for example palaeography and epigraphy). In this study, the sources were examined for authenticity focussing on the source itself (physical techniques were not used) and asking if the source is what it purports to be (Wood 1990:85).

Internal criticism is concerned with the meaning of statements in a source and establishing the credibility of details in a document (Gottschalk 1958:139-171; Shafer 1980:149-170). The method of internal criticism involves analysing the particular details of a document to understand, initially, the literal sense of the words, given the place and time of the author. Then context is considered by interpreting a statement in view of what precedes and what follows it (Shafer 1980:150-151). Gottschalk (1958:150-171) and Wood (1990:89-90) emphasise the following principles and tests for evaluating the credibility of sources:

1. The temporal proximity of the record to the event: as time lapse between the observation of an event and its documentation increases, the potential for distortion in the record also increases. When was the report made in relation to the event?
2. The purpose of the record: why was the document written and what was its intended audience? Was the witness willing to tell the truth? What were the author's intentions in writing the record? Greater confidence can be placed in incidental or casual information and statements irrelevant to the author's (overt and covert) agendas.
3. The state of the witness: Was the witness able to tell the truth? Experts and amateur witnesses differ widely in their ability to report specialist details. If the person was not an eyewitness, what is the source of the information? Are there internal contradictions?
4. Corroboration: Is there any independent corroboration of the details? Is the document similar to other translations and transcriptions? Do the details of the document conform with other historical or scientific facts?

In the context of this study, the written textual sources were sets of data on subsistence behaviours and narrative details that have already been interpreted and manipulated by the authors of the texts. By evaluating the degrees of authenticity and

reliability of the written textual sources, it was possible to gain a better understanding of the authors' influence on the data contained in the texts.

Historical sources

The journal of the fleet commander, Francisco Pelsaert, is the most substantial source for information on the voyage and crisis. There is some question regarding the possibility of Pelsaert dictating his journal to a scribe, which may have affected the journal's content. The original autograph manuscript (preserved in The Hague) is in an identical script to Pelsaert's other papers (van Huystee 1998). However, the script of the journal is different to Pelsaert's last letter to the VOC directors (van Huystee 1998:1). Roeper (1993) notes that the script and signature in Pelsaert's last letter to the VOC directors matches Pelsaert's signatures in the journal. From this evidence, Roeper concludes that the journal was not written by Pelsaert but by Salomon Deschamps, who was aboard the *Batavia* and presumably transcribed Pelsaert's daily notes into the surviving journal (Roeper 1993; van Huystee 1998:1). Only entries made following the wreck survive: those predating the shipwreck were thrown overboard during the shipwreck (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:185-186). The text was translated into English by Siebenhaar (1897; Terry 1994), Drok (Drake-Brockman 1963) and van Huystee (1998) but no critical analysis of Pelsaert's account has been published in English. The three English translations were found not to differ significantly. In this study, references to Pelsaert's journals are to Drok's edition (Drake-Brockman 1963) for consistency and because it is the only readily accessible published version.

Pelsaert kept a daily log of detailing weather conditions, the course of the ship and the activities of the passengers and crew. The most important duty of the commander (from the Dutch *commandeur*, a term with no maritime significance, accorded to senior VOC merchants in certain circumstances) was to keep an account of the voyage and execute the instructions and assignments of the VOC directors (Drake-Brockman 1963:5; Jacobs 1991:38). When the commander returned to Amsterdam his journals were filed with the VOC and archived (Bruijn, Gaastra and Schoffer 1987:196-201; Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:47, 263). Pelsaert's *Batavia* journals were intended for the directors of the VOC and consequently may contain distortions regarding Pelsaert's liability for the shipwreck and attempt to justify his absence during the mutiny. For example, Pelsaert glosses quickly over his abandonment of the

survivors on Beacon Island, and may have minimized sectarian aspects of the mutiny to escape personal criticism and protect the Calvinist orthodoxy of the VOC (Tylor 1970:41). If Roeper's evaluation of the handwriting is correct, then the text may be further biased by Deschamps' editing. Deschamps (who was involved in the mutiny, Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:223, 231) may have covered up questionable aspects of Pelsaert's management of the situation in exchange for favorable treatment during his trial.

Although Pelsaert's willingness for accuracy can be questioned, there is little doubt of his competence in keeping a journal. He was experienced in providing records for the VOC having previously written a lengthy journal (*Remonstrantie*) for the VOC relating his seven years of experience of Indian culture and trade (Moreland and Geyl 1925; Drake-Brockman 1956; 1963:22-34).

It is important to note that Pelsaert's account of the mutiny was reconstructed from the confessions of the mutineers under torture. Pelsaert did not experience first-hand the massacre that occurred after the shipwreck. Four days after the wreck Pelsaert, Jacobsz (the *Batavia* skipper) and seven other men left the Abrolhos Islands on a small boat to search for water and provisions (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:127-128). Unable to find water on the mainland or nearby islands, they sailed on to Jakarta and returned to the Abrolhos ninety-seven days after their departure (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:141). Pelsaert was absent from the islands during the critical period of the mutiny erupting and the division of the survivors into two groups. After Pelsaert's return to the Abrolhos Islands he conducted an investigation and interrogated the mutineers. Following standard Dutch juridical procedure, the mutineers were trialed, tortured and then hanged or marooned (Drake-Brockman 1963:96-99).

The account of the crisis provided in the confessions of the mutineers is inevitably biased as the mutineers would have attempted to avoid further punishment. Details of subsistence behaviours in the mutineers' confessions may be distorted or neglected where the mutineers feel it will lessen their punishment.

The letters of the predicant and the two passengers are shorter than Pelsaert's journal but have the advantage of being direct eyewitness accounts. The predicant, Gijsbert Bastiaensz, was the official minister on board the *Batavia*. His letter records

experiences with each of the two groups over the course of the crisis until Pelsaert's return. He was an experienced VOC predicant, having travelled on several previous voyages (Drake-Brockman 1963:77). Bastiaensz sailed on the *Batavia* with his wife and seven children. During the course of the mutiny only one member of Bastiaensz's family (the eldest daughter) was not murdered (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:265; Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:180-181). The predicant's letter is an intensely personal account of the mutiny and subsequent events, including details of the shipwreck, the shortage of resources on Beacon Island, and events on Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island. Bastiaensz writes about the malevolent personalities of the mutineers and the letter reveals his suffering at the loss of his family and personal discomfort. The purpose of the letter is (not surprisingly):

...to warn the Honourable High and Mighty Lords, at all occasions to have trustworthy, and Godfearing persons in their employment, especially Merchants and Skippers, everything depends on that; for it must be said that that is of the highest importance (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:269).

Bastiaensz's letter was written in 1628 while he was in Jakarta and is addressed to his relatives in Holland, informing them of the 'happenings on the journey' (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:263). Bastiaensz does not discuss events of the voyage prior to stop at the Cape and refers the reader to the section of Pelsaert's journal that deals with the outward voyage, unaware that it was destroyed during the shipwreck (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:263). The predicant does not mention the records Pelsaert kept during the trials of the mutineers or the other passengers' letters. The letter is biased by the predicant's focus on his own experience and his distress over the loss of his family. Bastiaensz writes that his letter is limited in length and detail because he had a short time to write it before the ship was to carry it to Amsterdam, and because his 'mind is still a little confused' over the incident (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:268).

The predicant's letter first appeared in the Hartgers 1648 edition of *Ongeluckige Voyagie van't Schip Batavia* (The Unlucky Voyage of the Ship Batavia), a popular seventeenth-century Dutch horror novel based on Pelsaert's journals (Drake-Brockman 1963:4, 78). The letter was included in subsequent editions, with an English translation made from the de Vries 1649 edition by E. D. Drok (Drake-Brockman 1963:263-269; Godard 1993:312-317). Although the predicant's letter has never been thoroughly analysed, it is probably genuine as it contains details unlikely to have occurred to a

seventeenth-century author-editor dealing with a horror story, and it clarifies and complements Pelsaert's account of the trials (Drake-Brockman 1963:79). The novel itself is largely compiled from Pelsaert's journals, transposed into the third person and considerably rearranged (Roepers 1993; Drake-Brockman 1963:4). English translations of the 1647 Jansz edition of the novel include Terry (1994) and Godard (1993). While the text of the novel contributes little to existing sources, several editions contain copper engravings of the survivors' camps (for example, figures 2.5-2.8). The drawings suggest a familiarity with the events and may have been drawn from an eyewitness account other than the text, although this possibility has not been investigated (Gibbs 1992:4; Drake-Brockman 1963:290). The drawings are consistent with other historical accounts, showing the survivors living in tents on both islands and a few barrels on Beacon Island after the wreck and before Pelsaert returned.

The letters of two *Batavia* passengers predate the novel by eighteen years, first appearing in a 1630 pamphlet called *Leyds Veer-Schuts Praetjen* (Leyden Ferry-boat Gossip). The sub-title of the pamphlet indicates the letters deal with the *Batavia* Undermerchant Jeronimus Cornelisz. Although signed with the same initials and not specifically addressed to anyone, the two letters must have had different authors. The first letter provides an eyewitness account of the events following the shipwreck including some details of subsistence and the numbers of people on each island (Stow 1972). The second letter is shorter and concentrates on describing the character of Cornelisz and the return voyage to Jakarta in the *Sardam* (Stow 1972). It is reasonable to accept the letters as reliable because they appear shortly after the event, contain plausible eyewitness details and are consistent with the other accounts. The veracity of the historical data in the letters is limited by their personal nature and the intention to expose the evilness of Cornelisz. It is not possible to be sure if the authors distorted the tale in order to blacken the character of Cornelisz or to enhance the drama of the events. The tone of these two letters is strongly religious and emotive, similar to the predicant's letter, where the authors accredit their survival to God's grace, and the mutineers' atrocities to the evil influence of Cornelisz. In contrast, Pelsaert's journal maintains detached objectivity.

The story of the *Batavia*

The *Batavia* was an armed merchant vessel built and used by the VOC, and was part of a fleet of seven ships travelling to Jakarta (Drake-Brockman 1963:38). The VOC was formed in 1602 from several competing Netherlands trading companies (Boxer 1965:23; Jacobs 1991:12). The Netherlands States-General gave the VOC monopoly over Dutch trade and navigation east of the Cape of Good Hope (Boxer 1965:25; Jacobs 1991:15). All European countries — except Portugal — chose monopoly companies as the most suitable form of organisation for trading with Asia. The length of the sailing route to Asia (six to eight months) and the two year trade-cycle (the time between ordering Asian commodities and the selling of these goods in Europe) required long-term commitment and expensive backing. This was best provided and controlled by the government (Gaastra and Bruijn 1993:177). The main aim of the VOC was the making of profit by Asian trade and to achieve this aim the Company built and fitted out ships, constructed forts, cities and harbours in Asia (Bruijn et al. 1987:1). By developing a vast network of trade and shipping, the Dutch Company was transformed into a territorial power, similar to the Portuguese in the sixteenth century and the English in the eighteenth century (Gaastra and Bruijn 1993:178). The VOC was 'virtually a state within a state' (Boxer 1965:25), authorised to wage war and make treaties with Asian rulers and rival traders (Jacobs 1991:15). One of hundreds of routine VOC trading voyages, the *Batavia* left the Dutch port Texel on or around the 29 October 1628, leading its fleet on a trading voyage to Jakarta via the Cape of Good Hope (Drake-Brockman 1963:38-39; Bruijn, Gaastra and Soffer 1979:60).

There are no extant descriptions of the provisions and cargo carried by the *Batavia*. From archaeological investigations and records of voyages similar to the *Batavia* it is possible to list some of the goods the *Batavia* carried. Artefacts recovered during excavations on the *Batavia* wreck suggest that the cargo included armaments and military equipment, ceramic and pewter wares, cloth, jewellery, silverware and bricks (Green 1989). Drake-Brockman (1963:84-93) shows that the *Batavia* carried large amounts of coins and valuable and jewels and ornaments. Cargo lists of other East Indiamen trading with Java in the seventeenth century indicate currency, cloth, armaments, tradesmen's tools and materials and exotic items were common cargo (Bruijn et al. 1987:221-245).

The provisions carried by the *Batavia* can be reconstructed from written instructions issued by the VOC in 1656 and in 1695 on supplying merchant vessels with victuals for voyages to Asia (Green 1977:375-376; Bruijn et al. 1987:214-18). Provisions for vessels such as the *Batavia* included barrelled meat (unspecified salted meat, beef, pork, herring or stockfish), livestock (live pigs and chickens), vegetables (peas and horse-radish), condiments (oil, vinegar and mustard), groats (ground oats), rice, biscuits, bread, cheese, water, beer, wine, brandy, butter, lemon and lime juices (for the prevention of scurvy), prunes, flour, barley (feed for livestock) and salt (figure 2.1, Green 1977:375-376; Bruijn et al. 1987:214-218). The 332 people on board (consisting of crew, male and female adult and children passengers, VOC officers, soldiers and cadets) shared these provisions, although officers were permitted spices and a greater variety of meats and cheeses (Bruijn et al. 1987:218).

It was necessary for ships bound to Asia to resupply during the voyage because they were unable to store enough fresh vegetables, meat and water for the whole voyage (Jacobs 1991:57). For this purpose, the VOC made the Cape of Good Hope a mandatory provisioning station in 1616, but did not build a permanent supply settlement there until 1652 (Gaastra and Bruijn 1993:192; Jacobs 1991:17). The *Batavia* visited the Cape on 14 April 1629, and Pelsaert notes that he went ashore at the Cape 'in search of beasts' (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:248). Pelsaert's hunting trip was probably supplemented by sheep, cattle and fresh vegetables acquired by trading with the Khoikhoi (Drake-Brockman 1963:40; Bruijn et al. 1987:107-118).

Trading with the Khoikhoi may have been facilitated by a VOC outpost at the Cape. An example of such an outpost is Oudepost 1 (occupied from 1669 to 1732) that acted as a trade post between passing ships and indigenous Khoikhoi pastoralist-foragers (Cruze-Urbe and Schrire 1991).

While Pelsaert was ashore arranging supplies, two senior officers of the *Batavia* breached several VOC regulations by having improper relations with a passenger, leaving the ship without permission and misbehaving while on board other ships in the fleet. The skipper of the *Batavia*, Arian Jacobsz, was observed having sexual relations with Zwaantie Hendrix, the servant of a passenger named Lucretia Jansz (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:161). Jacobsz and Zwaantie went ashore with Undermerchant Jeronimus Cornelisz (the most senior VOC officer on board in the absence of Pelsaert) and then visited two others ships in the fleet. The three behaved 'very pugnaciously'

Item in Dutch	English	Quantity and Distribution
<i>Brood</i>	bread	175 000 pounds per hundred persons, this being sufficient for ten months
<i>Vleesch</i>	meat (beef)	six barrels of meat at 540 pounds per hundred persons
<i>Spek</i>	pork	6000 pounds for every hundred persons
<i>Vich</i>	dried and salted fish	500 pounds dried cod per hundred persons, 200 pounds of salted fish per hundred persons
<i>Kaas</i>	cheese	400 cheeses per hundred persons, meaning 4 cheeses of 7 to 8 pounds each, which they must keep and preserve for themselves according to the ships' articles and may consume as needed
<i>Water</i>	water	53 <i>toelasten</i> of 32 456.2 litres for each hundred persons
<i>Bier</i>	beer	25 barrels (one barrel roughly 153 L) per hundred persons, to be consumed during the early part of the voyage
<i>Fransche wijn</i>	French wine	4 half <i>leggers</i> of 256 <i>mingelen</i> (4 barrels of 307 L each, one <i>mingelen</i> being 1.2 L) per hundred persons, for distribution to the sick
<i>Spaansche wijn</i>	Spanish wine	3 <i>toelasten</i> containing 512 <i>mingelen</i> (3 times 614.4 L) per hundred persons
<i>Brandewijn</i>	brandy	3 <i>toelasten</i> per hundred persons in 24 barrels of 76.8 L
<i>Boter</i>	butter	3 barrels of butter of 360 pounds nett per hundred people, for use with fish and the cooked meal
<i>Oyle</i>	oil	7 half <i>aamen</i> of oil (7 times 76.8 L) per hundred men
<i>Azijn</i>	vinegar	4 <i>varkens</i> or half <i>leggers</i> (barrels of c. 300 L each) per hundred persons
<i>Limoensap</i>	lemon juice	1/4 <i>aam</i> of 32 <i>mingelen</i> (38.4 L) per hundred persons
<i>Sieroop</i>	treacle	300 pounds for one hundred persons
<i>Ronde pruymen</i>	prunes	2000 pounds of prunes per hundred persons
<i>Rijst</i>	rice	8 <i>sakken</i> (648 L) per hundred persons
<i>Gort</i>	groats	105 sacks (8505 L) of groats
<i>Grauwe erwten</i>	yellowpeas	4 sacks (324 L)
<i>Groene erwten</i>	greenpeas	10 sacks (810 L) per hundred persons
<i>Mosterdzaad</i>	mustardseed	half a barrel per hundred persons
<i>Grof zout</i>	coarse salt	(not listed, the salting of meat on board was abolished after 1679)
<i>Zeugen</i>	sows	4 live full size sows or 12 young pigs, after 1731, 18 hogs were to be supplied instead of sows
<i>Hoenders</i>	poultry	40 hens for a large ship

For the cabin and the sick small quantities of the following were provided:

Gouda and cumin cheeses, smoked hams and tongues, currants, raisins, cumin, aniseed, pepper cloves, nutmeg, mace, cinnamon, ginger, rusks and saffron

Figure 2.1
List of possible provisions carried by the *Batavia*

This list is based on instructions for provisioning ships issued by the VOC directors in 1695 and added to in 1702, 1706, 1708, 1712, 1713 and 1724 (Bruijn, et al. 1987:214-218). The supplies are meant for nine months, except for bread, which was intended for ten. The pound is the Amsterdam pound of 0.4941 kg.

(presumably drunken fighting), and their drunken behaviour worsened until they returned to the *Batavia* at midnight (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:121). The next morning, in the presence of Cornelisz and other officers, Pelsaert reproved and threatened Jacobsz for his actions. Jacobsz and Cornelisz were offended by Pelsaert and resentful of the public reproach Jacobsz received. Pelsaert had previously rebuked Jacobsz in 1628 at Surat, which may have contributed to the antagonism between them aboard the *Batavia* (Drake-Brockman 1956; 1963:33; Pelsaert in Drake Brockman 1963:163-164). According to their confessions (extracted under torture), after that day Jacobsz and Cornelisz immediately resolved to kill Pelsaert and most of the passengers and use the ship for pirating as soon as they could (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:153, 161, 195, 248).

Soon after leaving the Cape, the fleet was caught in a storm and the *Batavia*, by accident or design, was separated from the other ships (Drake-Brockman 1963:40). Also, Pelsaert fell ill and was bedridden for twenty days, unable to exercise his authority over the officers (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:249). During Pelsaert's illness and convalescence Jacobsz and Cornelisz had tried to convince other officers and crew-members to participate in their plans to mutiny. The skipper (Jacobsz) organised some crewmen and soldiers to anonymously assault Lucretia in an attempt to precipitate a mutiny by testing Pelsaert's ability to exercise his authority and punish the crew (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:250). According to the forced confession of Cornelisz, Jacobsz intended to alienate the crew and soldiers from Pelsaert by forcing him to take harsh disciplinary measures (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:250). Jacobsz had hoped to stand against Pelsaert in defence of the crew and soldiers and depose him as commander, but the lack of cohesion and planning among the soldiers and crew thwarted the mutiny (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:251). Pelsaert's authority over the crew, already weakened during his illness, became ambiguous after the assault on Lucretia. A small group of officers, crew and soldiers appear to have been protecting the offenders, reluctant for the issue to be investigated, while passengers and crew not involved in the mutiny plans were concerned that Pelsaert was unwilling or unable to discipline and punish the offenders.

There is no record of further incident until two hours before dawn on 4 June 1629, when the *Batavia* ran aground at the southern end of the Wallabi Group of the Houtman Abrolhos, sixty kilometres off the coast of Western Australia (figures 2.2, 2.3).

Figure 2.2

Map showing route of the *Batavia* from the Cape of Good Hope to the Abrolhos Islands, and the route of the open boat to Java and the route of the *Sardam*, from Roeper (1993). Original in Dutch.

Figure 2.3

Map of Wallabi Group, Houtman Abrolhos, from Green (1977)

Pelsaert records that he was still ill when he was thrown out of his bunk by the force of the collision with Morning Reef (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:122). The skipper, who was on watch at the time, claimed that he thought the surf on the reef was the shine of the moon (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:122). Without chronometers, no vessel of the seventeenth century was able to accurately fix longitude, so it is difficult to determine if the *Batavia* was deliberately wrecked as part of Jacobsz and Cornelisz' mutiny plan or simply an accident.

The crew became busy as the standard repertoire of techniques was employed to try and free the ship from the reef. The surrounding water depth was found to be very shallow, and the cannons were thrown overboard to make the ship lighter in an effort to float it off the reef. Anchors were put out to try and pull the ship free. It was hoped by the passengers and crew that the ship had wrecked at low tide, and the rising waters would lift the ship off the reef. As the sun rose, the opposite was found to be true, and the water was so rough about the ship that it was difficult to stand or walk on board. Adding to the confusion, the mainmast was cut down in an attempt to lighten the vessel, but fell onto the ship rather than away from it, causing damage and crowding the decks with tangled rigging (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:123-124).

Pelsaert sighted two small islands nearby, and after sending the skipper out to inspect them, ferried people out from the wreck. Three trips landed 180 people, 20 casks of bread and some small barrels of water (roughly 130 litres in total) on a low 5.25 hectare accumulation of coral rubble with no sources of water and spindly vegetation (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:124; Bevacqua 1974b:62; Green and Stanbury 1988:5-6). The survivors, sheltering in makeshift canvas tents, called this island *Batavia's* Graveyard, although it was officially named Goss Monument from 1897 until 1968 when it was changed to Beacon Island (Bevacqua 1974a:76). The only edible fauna on this island were small reptiles and visiting seabirds including the Little Shearwater that nest in abundance from April to December, laying a single egg between early July and late August (figure 2.4, Storr 1965; Storr, Johnstone and Griffin 1986:18). Sea lions were formerly abundant on the Abrolhos, providing a high protein source of food (Gales 1992; 1994). In 1843 John Gilbert recorded that:

all the islands in this group [Wallabi] are very thickly inhabited by the seal; we frequently come upon groups of 7, 8, and nine lying asleep on the sandy beach (Gilbert 1843).

	Common name	Scientific name	References	Distribution
Introduced mammals	Cow	<i>Bos taurus</i>	Edwards (1966)	Beacon Island
	Sheep/goat	<i>Ovis/Capra</i> sp	Edwards (1966), Storr (1965)	Beacon Island
	Horse	<i>Equus</i> sp	Green and Stanbury (1988)	W Wallabi Island
	Cat	<i>Felix</i> sp	Dakin (1919)	sparse
	Rat	<i>Rattus rattus</i> or <i>norvegicus</i>	Dakin (1919)	widespread
Native mammals	Tammar wallabi	<i>Macropus eugenii</i>	Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman (1963:235-236)	E and W Wallabi only
	Sea lion	<i>Neophoca cinerea</i>	Stokes (1846)	widespread
	Rat	<i>Rattus glauerti</i>	Alexander (1922)	sparse
Fish	Pink snapper	Sparidae <i>Pagrus auratus</i>	Alexander (1922)	widespread
	Blue-lined emperor	Lethrinidae <i>Lethrinus nebulosus</i>	Alexander (1922)	widespread
	Parrot fish	Scaridae <i>Scarus rubriviolaceus</i>	Alexander (1922)	widespread
	Wrasse	Labridae genus	Alexander (1922)	widespread
	Black snapper	Serrranidae <i>Malcoro niger</i>	Alexander (1922)	widespread
Birds	Wedge-tailed Shearwater	<i>Puffinus pacificus</i>	Alexander (1922), Storr et al. (1985)	W Wallabi Island
	Little Shearwater	<i>Puffinus assimilus</i>	Alexander (1922), Storr et al. (1985)	Beacon Island
	Pied Cormarant	<i>Phalacrocorax varius</i>	Alexander (1922), Storr et al. (1985)	widespread
	Great-winged petrel	<i>Pterodoma macroptera</i>	Alexander (1922), Storr et al. (1985)	widespread
	White-breasted Sea Eagle	<i>Haliaeetus leucogaster</i>	Alexander (1922), Storr et al. (1985)	widespread
	Lesser Noddy	<i>Anous tenuirostis melanops</i>	Alexander (1922), Storr et al. (1985)	widespread

Figure 2.4
Common fauna of the Wallabi Group, Houtman Abrolhos, Western Australia.

In the reef complex surrounding the islands there is an abundance of easily accessible and diverse species of fish and crustaceans (Gibbs 1992:3; Storr 1965; Hatcher 1985).

On board the wreck, drinking and rioting started, and Pelsaert's journal papers were thrown overboard. The resulting chaos made it difficult to salvage water and food (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:124). By the second day, 220 people were ashore, 180 on Beacon Island and 40 on Traitors Island, with 70 people (including Cornelisz) still on the wreck. Pelsaert, stationed on Traitors Island, noted with distress that the survivors on Beacon Island were not rationing the limited water supplies (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:124). The survivors on Beacon Island protested to Pelsaert that there was not enough water and complained about his inaction. Pelsaert discussed the options with the survivors on Traitors Island. They decided it was pointless to retrieve supplies from the wreck because any intact barrels would probably float ashore or be trapped in the wreck. Nearby islands and the mainland were considered by Pelsaert to be likely sources of water. If water was not found while sailing around nearby islands, Pelsaert planned to sail on to the port of Batavia at Java and arrange for a rescue vessel. Pelsaert intended to tell the survivors on Beacon Island of the plans, but claimed he was restrained by his companions. Pelsaert's companions feared that he might be taken hostage by the starving, thirsty and now quite aggressive survivors (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:127-127).

Pelsaert, Jacobsz and seven others left to inspect the other islands in the Wallabi Group on the third day after the shipwreck (6 June). They found only brackish water on West Wallabi Island where they were joined by eleven survivors in a boat from Beacon Island. The two boats sailed onto the mainland until the seventh day when the eleven survivors from Beacon Island returned to the Abrolhos Islands. Pelsaert failed to find any adequate water sources at the mainland and on the 12th day after the shipwreck (15 June), resolved to sail on to Java. Under VOC regulations, the commander was supposed to stay with survivors and send the skipper for help. Pelsaert, however, suspected that if Jacobsz was in command of the rescue attempt he might leave everyone to die and become a privateer or mercenary with the Portuguese or Spanish (Marsden 1974:202). Presumably Pelsaert hoped to assure the rescue of the survivors by accompanying Jacobsz on the voyage. If Pelsaert was fully aware of Jacobsz and

Cornelisz' intentions in the assault on Lucretia, it is difficult to understand why he did not take Cornelisz (and some loyal soldiers to guard him) to Java.

At this point, the survivors left on the Abrolhos were distressed by Pelsaert's abandonment and low on water and food. The predicant wrote that on Beacon Island they had no water or wine for four or five days and some were driven to drink their own urine with many dying of thirst (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:264). Fortunately, the onset of winter brought heavy rains to the Abrolhos and the rough weather burst the wreck and allowed barrels containing 2500 litres of water, 600 litres of French wine, 2700 litres of Spanish wine and 600 litres of vinegar to float ashore. Pelsaert and Bastiaensz record that the rainwater was collected, but like the wine was not rationed and did not last long (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:145; Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:260).

The heavy rains and rough weather also forced those still clinging to the wreck to try and swim ashore. Only 30 of the 70 left on the wreck made it to the islands, including the authors of the two letters found in the *Leyden Ferry-boat Gossip* pamphlet (Stow 1982:8). The last to leave the wreck was apparently Jeronimus Cornelisz, who floated ashore eight or ten days after the shipwreck (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:158). As the most senior VOC officer amongst the survivors, Cornelisz was expected by the survivors to bring order to the situation and organise the provision of rations (Tyler 1970:34; Stow 1972:8). For three weeks, while water and food was still relatively plentiful, Cornelisz 'behaved himself very well' and the other survivors appeared to be relatively content (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:264; Stow 1972:8).

In the three weeks of peace, Cornelisz was establishing his council of conspirators in a reproduction of the shipboard authority structure, presumably planning their activities (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:181-182; Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:264). The first action of Cornelisz and his council was ostensibly sensible; to send groups of survivors to other islands in search of food and water thus relieving the some of the pressure on the resources at Beacon Island (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:159; Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:264; Stow 1972:8). Approximately one week after Pelsaert's departure, several small groups of survivors were provided with some food and water and spread across Traitors Island (15 people), Seals Island (now called Long Island, 45 people) and East and West Wallabi Islands

(collectively known as High Island, 22 people) (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:45, 159). During Pelsaert's interrogations it was revealed that in dispersing the survivors, Cornelisz' malevolent intentions were to reduce in the number of survivors to 40 by murdering and stranding the rest. When there were about 40 survivors left, Cornelisz and his loyal followers hoped to capture the rescue vessel and use it for privateering or mercenary activity (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:159). Twenty-nine days after the shipwreck, the first murders were committed in secret under cover of darkness on Beacon Island. Shortly after, people on Beacon Island, Traitors Island and Seals Island were attacked and murdered by members of Cornelisz' council and their accomplices (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:173).

The historical documents variously say that Cornelisz was inspired by the Devil, or denied the existence of the Devil, Hell, God and Angels. The sources also suggest that Cornelisz was influenced by the Dutch painter Torrentius, who has a reputation of being an Adamite leader and a Rosicrusian (both were considered radical and heretical sects to the seventeenth century Dutch Calvinist) (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:212, Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:268; Stow 1972:10; Drake-Brockman 1963:73-75). Tyler (1970) and Marsden (1974:203) have suggested that Cornelisz organised his council into an Adamite or Anabaptist sect, both heretical groups in the Calvinist orthodoxy prevalent in the seventeenth-century Netherlands. Cornelisz used terror as a disciplinary weapon, murdering those who opposed him or disobeyed him. He drew up a constitution and pacts which Gibbs (n.d.) has suggested were an attempt to change the basis of authority away from the shipboard structure to one which legitimised his actions and those of his followers. He dressed himself and his council 'splendidly' with salvaged finery and forced female survivors to be concubines for him, his council and his followers (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:143, 146-147; Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:266-267).

Cornelisz and his followers murdered about 125 people, including men, women (some pregnant), children and infants throughout the Wallabi Group over about 33 days. The twenty-two survivors (mostly loyal VOC soldiers) initially sent to East Wallabi Island were intended by Cornelisz to starve and perish, and were ignored until the bulk of the massacre was over. The soldiers in fact found water on West Wallabi Island and, as arranged, signalled with three fires but were ignored while the massacre was in progress. The soldiers were joined by other survivors who managed to escape the carnage bringing the numbers to about 47, and informing the soldiers of the

massacre (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:143). At this stage a definite polarisation of the survivors is evident: Cornelisz and followers on Beacon Island, having decimated their opposition and bystanders, are now pitted against the loyalist soldiers and survivors on West Wallabi Island led by Weibbe Hayes.

West Wallabi Island is the largest island in the Wallabi Group, and has abundant edible native fauna and sinkholes of drinkable water. It is roughly 600 hectares of relictual continental surfaces overlain by limestone pavement, boulders and shingle, covered in places by dunes (Storr, Johnstone and Griffin 1986:7; Storr 1965; Teichert 1947; Dakin 1919). Although much of the rich vegetation on West Wallabi Island is inedible or unpalatable, several species of bird are resident there (including the Pied Cormorant, White-breasted Sea Eagle and Lesser Noddy), and it is visited in large numbers by nesting seabirds (in particular the Wedge-tailed Shearwater) (figure 2.4; Storr, Johnstone and Griffin 1986). The seabirds breed in abundance from August to November, excavating nest burrows up to 30 cm deep in the coral grit and lining the burrows with foreign material (Bevacqua 1974b:2; Storr, Johnstone and Griffin 1986:17, 40).

A unique subsistence advantage for the survivors on East and West Wallabi Islands over survivors on other islands in the Wallabi Group was the presence of the tamar wallabi. The tamar is confined to East and West Wallabi Islands with the population (in 1960) on West Wallabi Island 'amounting to some hundreds' and much less on East Wallabi Island (Storr 1965:10). When Stokes (1846:156) visited West Wallabi Island in 1840, he noted the abundance of tammars and his officers killed 76 of them over four hours at Slaughter Point. The tamar would probably have been an abundant source of food for the survivors. A small native rat and 'abnormally dense populations' of small reptiles are also found on West Wallabi Island (Storr 1965:8; 11). As with Beacon Island, sea lions, various fish and crustaceans were readily available to the survivors from the surrounding waters. West Wallabi Island has several sinkholes of drinkable water that rise and fall with the tide levels.

The historical sources indicate that the survivors exploited nearly all types of fauna on and around West Wallabi Island. The predicant writes that the survivors on West Wallabi were provided:

with water, with fowls, with fish, with other beasts [possibly sea lions], with eggs in basketfull [sic]... also some beasts which they called cats [tammars] and with as nice a taste as I ever tasted (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:267).

The author of the first *Leyden Ferry-boat Gossip* letter is even more hyperbolic about native resources on West Wallabi Island:

...we could well have lived there a hundred years with ten thousand men. In one day we could catch five hundred birds like doves, and each bird had an egg with her, as big as a hen's egg [*Puffinus* species]. As well, we caught hares [tammars], the like of which were never seen alive and were better tasting than chicken meat, of which every man could catch daily 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and sometimes more for his dinner. We also found fish called Stonebream, forty in the space of an hour, as big as Cod. We found wells which were 50, 60 fathoms and 100 and more deep, being very sweet water. (Stow 1972:9).

Pelsaert makes detailed (though not entirely accurate) notes on the tamarin, mentions two sinkholes containing drinkable water and the abundance of various types of fish and birds at West Wallabi (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:235-236).

The documentary sources present a picture of relative ease in the provision of subsistence resources for the survivors on West Wallabi Island. For the other survivors, the sources are not so clear, providing only sketchy data on subsistence at Beacon Island. Pelsaert mentions that barrels of bread, water, wine and vinegar from the wreck floated ashore at Beacon Island and were salvaged from the wreck (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:124-125, 215). The engravings in *The Unlucky Voyage of the Ship Batavia* show barrels floating near the islands, and two barrels ashore on Beacon Island, although this may be artistic license (figures 2.5, 2.6). Pelsaert's journal records various people on Beacon Island catching birds, frying fish and hunting, cooking ('boiling') and eating sea lions (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:196, 199, 175, 232, 233, 241, 244). The mutineers appeared to have hoarded resources on Beacon Island and organised a division of labour to maintain supplies. The predicant describes how Cornelisz hoarded food, inviting starving individuals to dine with him while his followers murdered the person's family (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:265). The predicant expresses that while on Beacon Island he was not permitted any of the available oil, vinegar, bread or rice, but allowed only a small amount of water. He says he was forced by hunger to eat grass and sea lions' skins (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:265). The mutineers appear to have used young boys to catch birds, and by controlling the movements of people they regulated who hunted for sea lions and who went fishing (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:145, 196, 199, 232, 233).

Figure 2.5

Engraving from *The Unlucky Voyage of the Ship Batavia* (figure eight in original). Beacon Island is on the left, with two barrels on the shore. The illustration depicts two boats ferrying people and possibly barrels from the wreck. The other island at the right is probably Traitors Island.

Figure 2.6

Engraving from *The Unlucky Voyage of the Ship Batavia* (figure seventeen in original). The illustration depicts the massacre on Beacon Island; note the wreck in the left foreground and the floating barrels.

The sources make no mention of any barrelled meat salvaged from the wreck, nor is there any suggestion of transfer of resources between the opposing groups on Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island. There is no evidence for cannibalism in the documentary accounts or excavated archaeological material. It is possible cannibalism was deliberately omitted from the records or kept secret by the mutineers.

The mutineers made several attempts to overcome Weibbe Hayes' group on West Wallabi Island, including bribery and three pitched battles (figure 2.7, 2.8). None were successful, with Cornelisz captured by Hayes' group and four mutineers killed in the second battle (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:253). Fourteen days later, on 17 September, the mutineers (who had all the weapons) made their third and final attack, under the leadership of Wouter Loos. After two hours of fighting at West Wallabi Island the *Sardam* appeared with Pelsaert and a group of soldiers on board. The mutineers were immediately taken prisoner without any resistance, and with Cornelisz they were kept under guard on Seals (Long) Island. While the trials were conducted Pelsaert ordered an extensive salvage operation (at the instruction of the VOC Governor-General) to retrieve anything of value from the wreck and the islands. Over the duration of the salvage operation and the trials (figure 2.9), Pelsaert indicated that they ate bread from the *Sardam*, vinegar salvaged from the wreck, tammars collected from East Wallabi Island, and birds and fish hunted from other islands in the Wallabi Group (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:214-217).

On 2 October, nine men were hanged on Seals (Long) Island and the salvage operations continued (figure 2.9). The 80-odd survivors left the Abrolhos on 15 November to return to Java. They stranded two mutineers on the mainland, and they returned to Java (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:299-230; Gerritsen 1995).

Figure 2.7

Engravings from *The Unlucky Voyage of the Ship Batavia* (part of figure 32 in original). Figure 2.7 depicts the predicant speaking to the soldiers on behalf of the mutineers in the boat. Figure 2.8 illustrates the mutineers attacking the soldiers on West Wallabi Island.

Figure 2.9

Engraving from *The Unlucky Voyage of the Ship Batavia* (part of figure 40 in original). The illustration depicts the hanging of convicted mutineers on Long Island.

Summary

The documentary sources indicate that while the causes and course of the insurrection are ambiguous, it is clear that two opposing social groups evolved on different islands with different subsistence resources. One group consisted of Cornelisz, his followers and bystanders (nearly of whom were murdered) stationed mainly on Beacon Island with very limited natural resources and some salvaged resources. The other group consisted of the loyalist soldiers and other survivors camped on West Wallabi Island. The documentary evidence suggests that the group on West Wallabi Island had no access to the wreck or salvaged resources and survived on tammars wallabies, abundant birds and their eggs, sea lions, and marine resources. The two groups did not share resources and there is no mention of any transfer of goods. When Pelsaert returned and restored some order, he collected subsistence resources from all over the Wallabi Group (including tammars) which were then consumed on Beacon Island and Long Island while the salvage operation and trials were conducted.

Chapter Three Site Formation Processes, Taphonomy and Recovery

Introduction

Since the *Batavia* survivors departed the Abrolhos, different events have contributed to the archaeological record including explorers, survivors of other shipwrecks, guano miners, and crayfishers (figure 3.1). This chapter describes both natural and human site formation processes from pre- and post-*Batavia* contexts. Particular attention is given to the taphonomic history of the faunal material to interpret how the *Batavia* survivors' faunal assemblage may have been modified between its deposition and my analysis. Taphonomy is the study of the formation of the archaeofaunal record (Efremov 1940; Lyman 1994a:1-9; 1982:337-340; Solomon 1990). In this project the two basic goals of taphonomic research were: 1) to identify the agents and processes that created the archaeofaunal record; and 2) to identify the faunal remains representative of the *Batavia* survivors' subsistence (Gifford 1981). This chapter concludes with a discussion of the impact of archaeological research on the survivors' camps, and a description of the recovery processes employed in acquiring the sample examined in this thesis.

Site Formation Processes

Recent natural site formation processes on the Abrolhos include the modification of the surface and subsurface by native fauna and movement of loose sand by strong weather systems. The nesting behaviours of shearwaters are a significant animal activity, involving the excavation of a burrow up to 30 cm deep and 50-100cm long (Storr, Johnstone and Griffin 1986:18). Added to this archaeologically alarming turbation process is the tendency of shearwaters to line their burrows with foreign objects. As a result, Bevacqua (1974b:2) notes that 'in the excavation, bits of modern English language newspapers were found in close proximity to musket balls'. Other animals also contribute to site formation processes. When the White-breasted Sea Eagle feeds on tammars, fish and other birds it devours its food on top of the flattened tops of rigid shrubs such as *Pittosporum phylliraeoides*, and the refuse then falls to the ground, giving the appearance of a midden site (Storr et al. 1986:23).

Figure 3.1
Overview of activities on Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island

Tammars, birds and reptiles contribute 'drop-deads' (animals that died by predation or other natural causes) and food remains to the matrix, which may be difficult to distinguish from human subsistence remains.

Prehistoric Aboriginal occupation of the Abrolhos Islands does not appear to have been long-term or intensive. Archaeological evidence is scant and inconclusive, however some Aboriginal artefacts have been recovered from Beacon Island suggesting that Aboriginal people visited the islands (Bevacqua 1974b:6). The islands may have been visited around 6,000-11,000 BP, during times of lower sea levels (Marwick n.d.). A small Eocene fossiliferous chert flake was excavated from Beacon Island in 1974. The source of the chert was probably submerged at c. 6,000 by rising sea levels, which also formed Beacon Island (Glover 1975; 1979; Teichert 1946). In 1984 Dortch and Morse (1984:41) surveyed East and West Wallabi Islands yet found no evidence for Aboriginal occupation. The islands, cut off from the mainland at 11,000-12,000 BP, 'were barren and inaccessible, and seldom or never visited by human beings during times of low sea level when they were tablelands near the western edge of a vast coastal plain' (Dortch and Morse 1984:41; Teichert 1946). Historic records suggest there were no signs of Aboriginal people ever having been on the islands.

The first known European visitor to the Abrolhos was by Frederik de Houtman who sighted and named the islands in 1619 (Drake-Brockman 1963:33). Shortly after the *Batavia* survivors left in 1629, several European vessels sighted the Abrolhos Islands. Two other Dutch vessels may have wrecked there (the *Ridderschap van Holland* in 1694 and the *Aagtekerke* in 1726), but so far there is no archaeological or historical evidence regarding these ships or any survivors' camps. The records of seventeenth-century visitors make no mention of any Aboriginal occupants or evidence of the *Batavia* wreck and survivors' camps.

The next documented visitors to the Abrolhos were the *Zeewijk* survivors. The *Zeewijk* ran aground at Half Moon Reef in the Pelsaert Group, the southernmost group of islands (figure 3.2). The survivors were stranded on Gun Island from June 1727 until February 1728, when they departed for Jakarta in a boat they had built (Green and Stanbury 1988:15; Ingleman-Sundberg 1977). The historical and archaeological evidence demonstrates that the *Zeewijk* survivors explored islands in the Pelsaert Group, yet there is no evidence that they ever visited the Wallabi Group (Bevacqua 1974d). Boranga's (1997) archaeological study of faunal remains from the *Zeewijk* survivors' camps is discussed in chapter five.

Figure 3.2
Map of Western Australia with an inset showing the Houtman Abrolhos, from Green (1989)

Throughout the nineteenth century, various scientific and commercial expeditions visited the Abrolhos. Captain Wickham, the commander of HMS *Beagle*, conducted an environmental survey of the islands in April 1840 and made considerable collections that are now in the British Museum (Alexander 1922:34). The British Museum collections contain specimens of tammars which only exist on East and West Wallabi, Islands (Alexander 1922:34). Also aboard the *Beagle* were Stokes and Pascoe who surveyed the islands and made detailed charts of the area. They found remains of the *Zeewijk* wreck near the southernmost group of islands and, believing it to be evidence of the *Batavia*, they mistakenly named the islands the Pelsart [sic] Group (Stokes 1846; Edwards 1966:91; 1998:85; Stanbury 1998:103-104). Stokes also found a bronze cannon and other Dutch artefacts on Gun Island that he correctly identified as the site of the *Zeewijk* survivors' camp (Stokes 1846:150; Stanbury 1998:104).

Stokes visited East and West Wallabi Islands, reporting wells of drinkable water and numerous tammars. Stokes and two companions killed 76 tammars in four hours at 'Slaughter Point' (Stokes 1846:156). Stokes, like John Gilbert (who was collecting specimens for Gould in 1843), did not document the two stone structures or record the wells on the eastern side of the island (Green and Stanbury 1988:11). Large guano deposits were reported by Stokes, which subsequently attracted commercial attention to the islands. Fishing and sealing became established industries on the Abrolhos during the 1840s and 1850s, mostly centred on the southern islands. Guano mining officially began in the 1870s with leases granted to John Bateman for Rat Islands and Charles Edward Broadhurst in the Pelsaert Group (Green, Stanbury and Gaastra 1998:appendix one). The guano industry in the Wallabi Group officially began in 1876 when L. A. Manning and Company were granted a two-year lease to remove guano. An illegal guano collecting expedition failed when the *Hadda* wrecked off Beacon Island in 1877. Captain Parker and crew stayed on the Wallabi Group for five days until they rowed to Geraldton (Henderson and Henderson 1988:222; Edwards 1966:92).

In 1879 and 1882 the Abrolhos were again surveyed for guano deposits by John Forrest. Forrest identified the *Zeewijk* survivors' camps on Gun Island and reported seeing 'the remains of two old stone huts and a well of good water ' on West Wallabi Island but does not record their locations (1879a; 1879b). In 1884, following Forrest's survey, Broadhurst, MacNeil and Company established industrial fixtures on Rat Island to remove guano from the islands (Stanbury, White, Heine and Potts 1993). A survey of guano deposits on the Wallabi Group

conducted by A. J. Wells in 1897 described a house, tramline and a jetty on West Wallabi Island (figure 3.3, 3.4, Green and Stanbury 1988:11; Storr 1965:4). These structures (and the activity on other islands) indicate that the guano industry was well established on West Wallabi Island in the early 1880s. Davis and Fallowfield took over from Broadhurst in 1904 and operated the guano industry of West Wallabi until 1915 when the industry closed down (Green 1972:44-54; Green, Stanbury and Gaastra 1998:153).

Guano collecting continued, along with frequent scientific visits, in the twentieth century. Naturalists, geologists and geomorphologists such as Campbell (1890), Saville-Kent (1897), Dakin (1919), Alexander (1922), Fairbridge (1947) and Teichert (1946) were attracted to the uniqueness of the Abrolhos as the southernmost coral reefs in the Indian Ocean (Stanbury 1998:107). Of these visitors, Saville-Kent was the only one to make notes on the Dutch artefacts he found on Gun and Rat Islands. Most of the industrial and scientific activity at this time appears to be concentrated on the Pelsaert Group (Stanbury 1998:107).

A new industry was established on West Wallabi Island in 1931 when T. C. Hoskins established the Cove Packing Company. The crayfish cannery works were located on the north side of the island adjacent to the guano-loading jetty. There has been little attention given to the early history of the crayfishing industry at the Abrolhos Islands. In 1933 the Red Tail Cannery was established on West Wallabi Island, but was unsuccessful (Wright 1992:68). During World War Two the crayfish industry on the Abrolhos Islands expanded as crayfish were provided for American troops (Sheard 1962:18). The crayfish industry continued to grow in the 1950s and 1960s as crayfish increasingly became a fashionable food (Wright 1992:69). Photographs taken on Beacon Island in the early 1960s show galvanised iron or asbestos shacks surrounded by sheds on Beacon Island (WAMM 74/74; O'Loughlin 1964; 1966; Hunneybun 1995:figures 4.9, 4.11). In 1998 Beacon Island had four camps with an approximate total of thirteen buildings, all along the eastern side of the island (figure 3.5).

Figure 3.3

Map of historic structures on West Wallabi Island, from Orme and Randall (1987)

Figure 3.4 Tattler Isl.

Map of historic features at Slaughter Point, West Wallabi Island, from Green (1966)

Figure 3.5
Aerial photograph of Beacon Island showing modern structures and vegetation coverage, from the Department of Land Administration survey for the Western Australian Maritime Museum, 1998.

Taphonomy

Natural processes on the Abrolhos affecting archaeological contexts include weathering and animal activity. Frequent action by strong winds and storms can potentially change the appearance and structure of exposed bones (Behrensmeyer 1978; Miller 1975:217). The exposure of bones is unpredictable, as bone may be buried for long periods in the loose sandy matrix, or continuously buried and exposed, or never buried at all, and eventually all three options (Foley 1981:170). Historical sources make no mention of specific food disposal practices for any period of occupation, so refuse might have been either buried, burnt or scattered. Although weathering is not well understood, it can be acknowledged as occurring in varying degrees in relation to time of exposure (Lyman and Fox 1989). The soil is alkaline, which assists in the preservation of bone (White and Hannus 1983; Chaplin 1971). There is no reason to believe diagenesis by extrinsic or intrinsic factors have significantly affected the bone on the Abrolhos (Lyman 1994a:417-433).

Along with weathering, Shearwater burrowing is a difficult to quantify taphonomic process. The nesting behaviour of the Shearwaters are important taphonomic processes, preventing good stratigraphic control and in some respects virtually eliminating the archaeological context of faunal remains. The density and distribution of burrows is not known, except that there are more on West Wallabi Islands than East Wallabi Island (Storr 1965:4). Dakin (1919:155) numbers the burrows on West Wallabi Island in the thousands and writes that 'it is not unusual for anyone trying to walk over this area to fall through with one foot or both at every other step'.

Other fauna on the Wallabi Group, such as reptiles and tammars on East and West Wallabi Islands, act as taphonomic agents by trampling, scavenging and contributing 'drop-deads'. Tammars do not scavenge because they are herbivores. The taphonomic processes contributed by reptiles and tammars are assumed to have had minimal effects on the *Batavia* survivors' faunal assemblages.

Aboriginal occupation has left a negligible trace, and probably contributed only slightly to the faunal assemblages and taphonomic processes relevant to this investigation.

The taphonomic processes contributed by the *Batavia* survivors are the central concerns of this project. The historical sources discussed in chapter two describe the survivors' subsistence behaviour, suggesting they killed and butchered sea lions, tammars, birds and fish. Historical records indicate the *Batavia* survivors cooked their meat, including frying fish and 'boiling' sea lion meat (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:196 199 175 232, 233, 241, 244). In this context, boiling may be an expression for sea lion meat frying in its own oil and fat. Food salvaged from the wreck of the *Batavia* by the survivors consisted of barrelled meat and bread. Assuming the historical records present a reasonably accurate account, taphonomic processes attributable to the *Batavia* survivors include butchering and burning of birds, fish, tammars, sea lions and barrelled meat. Bone fragmentation may have been increased through the extraction of marrow and toolmaking. In this study these processes were assumed to be indicators of the survivors' subsistence behaviours, and were the focus of the analysis. One of the themes in this analysis of the faunal material was to identify and exclude taphonomic processes not related to the *Batavia* survivors to remove evidence that does not reflect the survivors' subsistence behaviours.

Most of the seventeenth- and eighteenth-century visitors to the Wallabi Group appeared to have stayed only a short time in small groups. Later explorers and scientists contributed to the archaeofaunal record by trampling over the islands and leaving their own food remains of native and salvaged fauna. The subsistence refuse of these visitors may have become incorporated into the *Batavia* faunal remains on Beacon Island. Mixing of assemblages is less likely on West Wallabi Island because there are no reports of the stone structures from the seventeenth- and eighteenth-century visitors. The absence of historic reports of the stone structures may suggest they were not visited although it is not possible to be certain.

Studies of trampling by humans and animals have recognised that it is an important process affecting the spatial and formal attributes of artefacts (Lyman 1994a:377; Schiffer 1983; 1987). Experimental studies show that bones can be size-sorted by trampling and displaced on both vertical and horizontal axes (Nielson 1991; Olsen and Shipman 1988). The degree of sorting and displacement depends on the nature and duration of the trampling and the type of soil (for example, loose or compact, coarse or fine, wet or dry). In Nielson's (1991:492) experiments bone was not badly damaged by trampling. Other studies show that trampling can damage bones (Myers, Voorhies and Corner 1980:487) and produce marks resembling types of tool-generated cut marks (Behrensmeier, Gordon, Yangi 1986; Fiorillo 1989).

When Stokes and his officers slaughtered tammars at Slaughter Point, West Wallabi Island in 1840 they may have caused an over-representation of tamarin skeletal remains in that area, provided they left the animals where they killed them. Slaughter Point is where the coastal stone structure attributed to Hayes' group is situated (figure 3.3, 3.4). Stokes' tamarin slaughter may have occurred near this shelter, although it seems unlikely as Stokes makes no mention of the shelter in his report. This is an argument from absence of evidence that could be refuted with finds of 'numerous Magnum 44 and shotgun shells' near the two Slaughter Point structures (Orme and Randall 1987:27). The shells may have resulted from the activities of Stokes or Dakin (1919:159), who reputedly shot four tammars with two shots in 1917, an indication of the tamarin's abundance. It is not known if the shells found correspond to weapons used by Stokes or Dakin. Archaeological investigations into the *Batavia* survivors at the coastal shelter have revealed no trace of nineteenth-century occupation, suggesting Stokes' slaughter had little effect on the faunal assemblage of the *Batavia* survivors (Bevacqua 1974c:15).

More intensive human transformation of the Wallabi Group Islands began with the guano industry in the early 1880s (figure 3.6, 3.7). Drawing on Helms (1902), Storr writes that:

...the extraction of the guano between 1884 and World War One involved the vegetation [sic] in large-scale disturbances. Before removing the guano, which mostly lodges among boulders of limestone, all plants were stripped from an area, the stones laid to one side, and the soil shovelled with hoes and with heavy brooms into heaps. (Storr 1965:4)

In 1959 all the old guano excavations were completely revegetated, with the guano industry represented by only the remains of a jetty, tramline, horse yard and 'some obviously unnatural hollows and heaps of stone in the dunes' (Storr 1965:4; cf. figure 3.6, 3.7). Modern maps of West Wallabi Island show the remains of old guano works and related infrastructure on the western side, distant from the two stone structures attributed to the *Batavia* survivors (figure 3.3, Storr 1965:2; Kirkman 1980). The total area modified by the guano excavations has not been mapped or documented, and it is possible the area of the stone shelters was disturbed. The field books of A. J. Wells indicate that the Southwest Field and Snake Flat were mined for guano, but as these areas were depleted, guano was collected from all over the island (Green and Stanbury 1988:11). Edwards (1966:93) relates that the guano industry employed 'Chinese' labourers (mostly actually from Timor) on West Wallabi Island who lived in huts at Pelican Point and maybe one of the two stone shelters at Slaughter Point. The labourers frequently

Figure 3.6

Guano mining in the nineteenth century on Rat Island, from Green (1972). Similar techniques were employed on islands in the Wallabi Group. Original in Battye Library.

Figure 3.7

Guano mining in the nineteenth century on Rat Island, from Green (1972). Original in Battye Library. These two figures illustrate some of the site formation processes involved in guano mining.

collected Dutch artefacts as they appeared during guano excavations in the Pelsaert Group, but apparently not in the Wallabi Group (Stanbury pers. comm. 1999).

Bevacqua (1974c:15) says that Dutch artefacts only were recovered from the coastal stone structure, but he states that the 1967 archaeological expedition found some surface ceramics dating to the late 1800s or early 1900s at the inland structure (Bevacqua 1974a:65). A retired local fisherman, Frank Burton, related that a stone structure (presumably the inland one) was used as men's quarters for labourers on the guano works during the early twentieth century (Bevacqua 1974a:65). There have been no archaeological investigations of the structures relating to the guano industry to confirm who the labourers were and where they lived. The surface of the inland structure has been examined and no Dutch artefacts were found (Stanbury pers. comm. 1999). The inland structure has not been excavated because it is built on bare exposed limestone bedrock and there is no deposit to excavate (Bevacqua 1974a:65).

In the context of this thesis, the guano industry on West Wallabi Island represents a set of taphonomic processes that included trampling, marking, spatial displacement, fragmentation, addition and removal of faunal material. Unfortunately, like other taphonomic processes on West Wallabi Island, it is difficult to establish the exact structure and extent of the taphonomic processes caused by the guano industry. The guano industry contributed food remains to the archaeofaunal record, possibly including cow, sheep, goat and horse (used on the railway line and presumably kept in the horse-yards). These faunal contributions should be most concentrated at the labourers' dwellings, but they could have been dumped anywhere on the island. Beacon Island was less affected by the guano industry because it has negligible guano deposits and was not intensively mined (Forrest 1879a; Gibbs 1992:5). Bevacqua (1974a:72-74) argues that the stone structure at the south-east end of Beacon Island (popularly known as 'Cornelisz' Prison') was built by the *Hadda* survivors in 1877 who camped there for five days.

Bevacqua's (1974a:72) list of material recovered during the 1967 excavations includes clay pipes, glass (including a mirror), ceramic, wood and metal. He claims that the site was not occupied by guano diggers, given the absence of guano deposits on the island and discussion of guano in historic sources. The absence of specialised paraphernalia suggests that fishermen and sealers were not long-term occupants of the Slaughter Point area (Bevacqua 1974a:73). The clay pipe fragments match with pipe types manufactured in England at 1850-1919, and the glass and ceramic resemble material from other nineteenth-century colonial wrecks such as the 1898

Sepia and the 1852 *Eglinton*. The mirror, pipe and a piece of jarrah found associated with the structure confirm that the site was occupied long after the *Batavia* survivors were on the island. It is possible that the Beacon Island stone structure was built by the *Batavia* survivors and occupied by later visitors who left an archaeological record. The taphonomic consequences of the structure being reoccupied are trampling and the addition of more faunal material (fauna salvaged from colonial wrecks and native fauna) to the original *Batavia* assemblage.

Today, crayfishers live on the islands in shacks. The population on Beacon Island varies, with most occupation occurring during the crayfishing season, from June to November (Gibbs 1992:19). After excavating on Beacon Island in 1992, Gibbs stated that:

The most significant phase of the [sic] Beacon Island's post-*Batavia* history, with particular relevance for the impact upon the archaeological record, has been the occupation of the islands by crayfishermen [sic] (Gibbs 1992:6).

There have been several phases in the modern use of Beacon Island, with activity patterns changing as the population grows, and building and salinity become increasingly regulated (Gibbs 1992:14). The modern fishing camps are situated along the island's eastern margin, currently occupying almost the same areas as the known distribution of seventeenth-century Dutch material (Gibbs 1992:19). The taphonomic processes contributed by the crayfishing industry are similar to other agents: trampling, spatial displacement, marking and possibly also burning. However, because the crayfishing population lives virtually on top of the *Batavia* survivors' camps, the impact is more focussed than other taphonomic agents. The construction of buildings and gardens means a significant though unmeasured level of disturbance has occurred in the area of the survivors' camps.

Another important taphonomic consideration is refuse from the crayfishing camps. After visiting Beacon Island in 1963, Edwards (1966:173) writes that waste from the crayfishing occupants consists of beef, mutton and fish: 'Rotting sheep heads, bullock hocks and fish, drying in the bait racks, waft putridly in the breeze'. Little is known about the waste disposal behaviours of the crayfishing occupants, and it is assumed here that some of their leftovers and bones were scattered in the gardens or surrounding area. Crayfisherman Dave Johnson (who discovered the *Batavia* wreck) says that he buried his waste, often coming across skeletons of *Batavia* survivors (Edwards 1966:168). The crayfishing community on West Wallabi Island appears smaller than Beacon Island, with scattered huts on the island's

northern side (Edwards 1966:174). Crayfishing activity on West Wallabi Island has probably had little impact on the *Batavia* survivors' faunal remains because the *Batavia* sites are on the other side of the island from the crayfishing camps.

Adding to these recent faunal additions is bait used in the crayfish pots. Tamar meat and macropods brought from Geraldton were used as baits, along with beef, mutton and goat meat (Edwards 1966:175; Stanbury pers. comm. 1999). Preparing meat for baits probably occurred in the sheds surrounding the shacks and involved butchering techniques to provide specific parts of animals, such as the sheep heads, bullock hocks and fish described by Edwards (1966:175). From a taphonomic perspective, the material results of the crayfishing industry obscures the *Batavia* survivors' faunal assemblage; the crayfishing industry disturbed the location of the faunal remains with buildings and activity, and contributes faunal material to the archaeofaunal record under examination. Unfortunately the taphonomic overprint of crayfishing is difficult to identify because accurate details of the crayfishing community's dietary habits have not been documented. Some details of butchering techniques employed in baiting traps have been recorded, but in a very brief account of a small sample. Change of diet and butchery in the crayfishing community may have occurred over time, but no records were available.

The process of understanding the taphonomic history to isolate the *Batavia* survivors' faunal material is problematic. Introduced species not carried on the *Batavia* (non-tamar macropods, horse and cow) and bones exhibiting modern and craybait butchery patterns (sheep heads, others unknown) were excluded from the sample under analysis, detailed in chapter five.

Recovery methods and past archaeological research into the *Batavia* survivors' camps

The final taphonomic agents considered in this project are the archaeologists (amateur and professional) who have investigated the Abrolhos Islands in search of traces of material from the *Batavia*. The first acknowledged archaeological finds relating to the *Batavia* came from Beacon Island in 1960. Following these discoveries there was a steady flow of investigations of the *Batavia*. Details of the various amateur and professional explorations are available in Stanbury (1998), Green and Stanbury (1988) and Edwards (1966). Archaeological activity relevant to the taphonomy and recovery of faunal remains is discussed in this section.

Although Dutch material was probably found by the guano workers, the first reported evidence of Beacon Island being the site of *Batavia's* Graveyard was provided by a skeleton discovered by crayfisherman in 1960 (Kirkman 1980:3; Stanbury 1998:107). Hugh Edwards, a Western Australian journalist, visited the island in the same year and found seal and bird bones in his excavations (Edwards 1966:104). In his description of the excavated material Edwards made no association between the bones he found and the survivors' subsistence behaviours. The wreck of the *Batavia* was discovered in 1963 and attracted more attention to the islands. Archaeology, practised with varied levels of expertise, became a popular activity on Beacon Island.

Edwards provides an account of his archaeological activity in 1963, with particular focus on the survivors' subsistence:

Digging strata-trenches across the island and shoveling [sic] the sand through sieves produces less gruesome relics of the old Hollanders. There were fire-blackened bird, seal and wallabi bones by the barrow load. The birds were mostly those of sooty-black mutton birds [Shearwaters] and fairy terns [*Sterna* species]... bones browned and blackened on old corals (1966:168).

Edwards also comments on the sea lion bones they found:

The Dutch saw them only as food... They must have killed many of the poor beasts with pike and club. The thick bones of the seals, some still carrying old knife nicks, are legion in their fireplaces. We emptied dozens of haunch and chop bones out of the sieves (1966:169).

The last sentence gives the impression that faunal remains were not always collected, but presumably re-deposited in or near the trenches (Gibbs 1992:8). The faunal remains that were collected during these excavations and stored in the Maritime Museum form part of the data-set for this project.

The resident crayfishing community became involved in archaeology, and visitors to Beacon Island occupied themselves with digging around the shacks for Dutch material (Gibbs 1992:7). Edwards' description presents an alarming picture of widespread uncontrolled and undocumented excavations:

Everyone on the island caught the digging bug. The Bevilaquas turned out with shovels and old Pop Marten, who found the first skeleton in 1960, though he was now in his 80's, was swinging a pick and turning over coral slabs with the rest of them. The Army men, bored with inactivity on the boat, came ashore and tried their hand. And between the multitudinous fragments of shell, coral and natural bird and animal bones, relics of the *Batavia* mounted (1966:169).

West Wallabi Island was less thoroughly investigated: no trace of Dutch occupation was found until 1964 when Edwards and group from Aquinas College located and excavated the two stone structures (O'Loughlin 1964).

There are no surviving records detailing the extensive investigations on Beacon Island in 1963, led by Chris Halls from the Western Australian Museum. Halls (1963:28) says the excavations (labelled E.S. "C") were carried out 'toward the northern end of the island', believed to be to the north and west of Bevilaqua's hut (figure 3.8, Green, Gaastra and Stanbury 1998:156). A trench called T.T.A was excavated between the huts of Johnson and Bevilaqua, with three trenches (A, B and C) coming off at right angles to T.T.A (Green, Gaastra and Stanbury 1998:156). The T.T.A trenches recovered no Dutch artefacts.

As a consequence of the extensive archaeological activities, the faunal remains from Beacon Island have been thoroughly disturbed. Over an unknown area, digging was conducted with shovels, and the occasional use of sieves of unknown sizes. Faunal material was collected or thrown away, with no explanation of method. The recovered material is biased by the low spatial resolution caused by using shovels and the absence of stratigraphy and detailed excavations reports. Bias also occurred on the recovery of different sized bone. Large bone (sea lion 'haunch and chop bones') seems to have been disregarded, while the shovel makes small bones difficult to excavate. The sieves, when used, may have recovered small bones but these bones do not seem to have been systematically collected.

Excavations on West Wallabi Island in 1964 were more thoroughly documented. A group of five staff and twelve students from Aquinas College investigated West Wallabi Island with two objectives:

1. To investigate a number of sites on West Wallabi and to verify if possible, that these sites were related to Weibbe Hayes' occupation of the Island.
2. To establish the subsistence diet of these castaways (O'Loughlin 1964:35).

The interior of the coastal stone structure and surrounding area at Slaughter Point was excavated to a depth of about 30 cm. Although the depth of the excavations was deemed too shallow to produce a section drawing, excavated material from the area surrounding the shelter was 'thoroughly sieved' with a sieve of anonymous size (figure 3.9, O'Loughlin 1964:36).

Figure 3.8
Map showing the approximate locations of some of the excavations carried out on Beacon Island, from Green, Gaastra and Stanbury (1998:appendix two)

Key			
1963	Cramer et al.	A	Fisheries/Museum building
1964	Edwards et al.	B	Dransfield's house
1967	Jack-Hinton et al.	C	Bevilacqua's house
1974	Bevacqua et al.	D	Johnsons's house
1980	Kirkman et al.	E	Royce's house
1994	Gibbs et al.	F	Stone structure "Cornelisz' prison"

Figure 3.9
 Plan of excavations at the Slaughter Point stone structure on West Wallabi Island from Bevaqua (1974a)

Various Dutch artefacts were recovered from the Aquinas excavations, including pottery and metal pieces at the same depth as the base of the stone structure. The artefacts and their association with the base of the structure indicate that the site was built and occupied by the *Batavia* survivors. The inland structure was investigated along with a well and several fireplaces, with no signs Dutch use evident (O'Loughlin 1964:36).

Animal bones recovered from the Aquinas excavations were identified as sea lion, tamar and shearwaters. The bones were 'recovered in medium quantity both inside and outside the structure', with burnt bones associated with two hearths at the same depth as the base of the structure and the other Dutch artefacts (O'Loughlin 1964:36). Without giving quantitative details, they claim that the faunal material was not 'in an expected quantity' and suggest that:

- 1) Food scraps were disposed of elsewhere, or 2) the main campfire, possibly some distance away, has not been discovered, or 3) this structure is not the main campsite (O'Loughlin 1964:36).

The discoveries made during the second Aquinas expedition in 1965 were 'more reassuring' in establishing the subsistence behaviours of the forty survivors who lived there for three and a half months (O'Loughlin 1966:12).

The 1965 Aquinas excavations of the coastal Slaughter Point structure covered a more extensive area than the previous year, and material excavated from the interior of the structure was sieved. Dutch artefacts were recovered, including ceramic and metal pieces. Pieces of lead appeared to have been worked, and some iron fragments were bent into fish-hooks (O'Loughlin 1966:12). The only faunal material mentioned is burnt tamar, apparently in a quantity judged (the methods are unstated) to sustain forty people for three and a half months (O'Loughlin 1966:12). The faunal material excavated by Aquinas College was not included in the faunal analysis of this project because the bones could not be found (Stanbury pers. comm. 1999) although chapter five includes discussion of relevant details.

Excavations of Beacon Island continued in 1967 with a group of about 20 University students led by Colin Jack-Hinton from the Western Australian Museum (Gibbs 1992:8). The Museum has no records or photographs of this expedition and none have been published (Stanbury pers. comm 1999). The area excavated in 1967 (named area "C") appears to be to the immediate east of Dransfield's house, in a shallow depression (Gibbs 1992:8; Stanbury, MacLeod and Gibbs 1992:16).

Artefacts recovered from area "C" include Dutch ceramic and metal fragments. According to Green and Stanbury:

a large quantity of midden material was recovered from the Site "C" surface area among which were butchered animal bones (1988:5).

Jack-Hinton also excavated the stone structure at the southern end of Beacon Island, recovering mainly nineteenth-century artefacts and some faunal remains (Green and Stanbury 1988:5). The faunal remains from area "C" and the southern stone structure were analysed as part of the current investigation.

Further excavations on Beacon Island were conducted by Bevacqua in 1974. A trench of one by six metres, called T.T.1, was excavated in the sandy interior of the south-east portion of the island, between Johnson's and Royce's huts (Bevacqua 1974b:2; Green and Stanbury 1988:5). Squares one and two were excavated in arbitrary levels, and the remaining four according to the natural stratigraphy. The stratigraphy consisted of 1) a surface of loose white sand and humus, 2) a layer of brown, compact and mixed with guano, 3) a sterile underlying strata of coral rubble with a sand fill (Bevacqua 1974b:2). Dutch ceramic, glass and metal pieces were recovered from this excavation (Bevacqua 1974b:6-9).

Bevacqua (1974b:2) appears to have been the first to note site disturbance due to the nesting behaviours of the shearwaters. Consequently, he states that 'Few food remains, with any certainty, can be attributed to human subsistence and none can be directly linked to the *Batavia* incident' (Bevacqua 1974b:5). The birds disturbed the stratigraphic record and introduced fish bones, 'drop-deads' and eggshells where midden material associated with the *Batavia* survivors would be expected to be found (Bevacqua 1974b:5). The presence of 'the disarticulated skeletons of several seals' in the midden is noted by Bevacqua (1974b:5). Although Bevacqua (1974b:9) states that 'the deposit had literally been riddled by shearwaters [that] made it difficult to determine whether the remains were the result of human activity or natural deposition', the faunal material from T.T.1 was included in this analysis of the *Batavia* survivors' subsistence behaviours.

The faunal assemblage from West Wallabi Island analysed in this investigation was excavated from the coastal structure by Bevacqua in 1974. A one by nine metre trench was pegged out across the structure, with six square metres excavated (figure 3.9, Bevacqua 1974c:67). The two trenches (A and B) excavated by Jack-Hinton in 1967 were reopened and slightly expanded by Bevacqua (Bevacqua 1974c:9). The loose sandy matrix consisted of 'homogenous sand and

semi-fossilised gastropods', and with no obvious stratigraphic layers the excavations were in arbitrary levels.

All excavated material was sieved using 0.65 cm sieves with all midden and artefactual material kept for 'later analysis' (Bevacqua 1974c:9). Twenty-seven artefacts were recovered, including nails, barrel hoops, lead, ceramics and glass. The excavations revealed a midden containing burnt bones of tammars, shearwaters and other birds, crabs, oysters and small amounts of sea lion (Bevacqua 1974c:11). Bevacqua (1974c:11) noted that his excavations contained no fish remains, and the Aquinas excavations also reported no fish. He suggests that the survivors on West Wallabi Island did not possess the means for procuring fish (Bevacqua 1974c:14-15).

Based on the excavated material, Bevacqua makes several inferences of the behaviour of the survivors. Because the food remains are all native to the island, Bevacqua (1974c:16) suggests a hunting and gathering lifestyle was adopted. As the local resources became depleted and seals and tammars became more wary of hunters, the group would need to travel further afield and hunt with greater determination (Bevacqua 1974c:17). The population of survivors increased over time as more people fled the mutineers, putting increasing stress on resources. Bevacqua (1974c:17) considers the Aquinas College find of iron fragments bent into fish hooks as evidence of attempt to exploit new subsistence resources to accommodate the increasing population. The survivors on West Wallabi Island organised themselves to defend themselves against the mutineers with weapons made from barrel hoops and nails (Bevacqua 1974c:17). Given the archaeological and historical evidence, Bevacqua (1974c:18) inferred that the group was organised after a military chain of command with a division of labour between defensive duties (on lookout, making weapons and fortifications) and camp duties (procuring and preparing food for the group).

In 1980 a six square metre trench (T.T.2) in the centre of Beacon Island was excavated by staff from the Western Australian Maritime Museum and students of the Post-graduate diploma in Maritime Archaeology (figure 3.9). The 1980 trench extended Bevacqua's T.T.1 excavated in 1974 (Kirkham 1980:7). Kirkham (1980:7-9) recorded exactly the same stratigraphy as Bevacqua, and similar types of artefacts, including Dutch ceramics, metal and glass. A very brief statement on the faunal remains relates that:

[of the] many fish and mammal bones that were excavated from the sites, few can be related to the Dutch survivors [such as] bones that have been charred or exhibit butchering marks (Kirkham 1980:10).

These bones were not included in the present analysis. Green and Stanbury (both present at the 1980 excavation) note that T.T.2 produced a 'dense deposit of artefacts and faunal material' but provide no details (Green, Stanbury and Gaastra 1998:158).

Subsequent archaeological investigations include surveys and excavations on Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island. Summaries of these investigations are available in Green, Stanbury and Gaastra (1998:appendix one and two) and Gibbs (1992:appendix one).

Summary

From an archaeological perspective, natural and human activities on the Abrolhos present a complex and poorly understood set of site formation processes. In this thesis it was important to recognise the disturbance of the shearwaters, the ambiguous nature of Aboriginal occupation, the impact of early explorers, guano collecting, crayfishing and other archaeological investigations. Archaeological sites on Beacon Island have been significantly altered by the crayfishing industries and previous (amateur and professional) archaeological investigations. The archaeological sites on West Wallabi Island appear to have suffered less disturbance possibly because they were protected by the stone structures and less affected by human activity. Taphonomic studies allow an understanding of the formation processes of the archaeofaunal record, and how irrelevant faunal material can be stripped away from the *Batavia* survivors' faunal remains.

Chapter Four Methods

Introduction

The objective of this analysis of fauna was to provide data on the subsistence behaviours of the *Batavia* survivors. The analysed sample consisted of 3436 specimens of bone from the 1974 and 1967 excavations on Beacon Island and 344 specimens from the 1974 excavations on West Wallabi Island. It is important to note that there are no records of the 1967 excavations and little is known of how the bones were collected and whether sieving occurred and if a 'representative' or 'total' sample was taken. The 1974 excavations used a 0.65 cm sieve, saving all faunal and artefactual material for later analysis (Bevacqua 1974d:9). This chapter explains the types of data collected from the bones and the methods employed during the analysis reported in chapter five.

The chief assumption in this project was that the sample analysed is representative of the target population (Fletcher and Lock 1991:64). The target population, in this case, is the faunal remains of the *Batavia* survivors. However, it is clear from the previous chapter that the analysed assemblages potentially contain faunal remains from a number of events unrelated to the *Batavia* survivors. In response to the problem of a 'contaminated' sample, attempts were made in this study to improve the resolution of the target population, and then use this target population to identify the survivors' subsistence behaviours.

Sorting and Cataloguing

The 1963 and 1974 faunal assemblages were initially sorted into categories of 'large mammal', 'small mammal', 'fish', bird' and 'unidentified'. Invertebrate fauna (shellfish) and non-faunal material had been removed by staff at the Western Australian Maritime Museum. The fauna was sorted and labelled by Museum staff according to the accession numbers used by the 1967 and 1974 excavators. A new inventory system was devised after Sinclair and Stanbury (1999) with each bone

labelled with letters denoting the location ('BCI' for Beacon Island and 'BAT' for West Wallabi Island) followed by a sequential number (for example, 'BCI 8', 'BAT 4735'), then suffixed by capital letters to identify different bones with the same number, thus; 'BCI 8C', 'BAT 4735U'.

Sample size and species richness

Species richness is here defined as the diversity of taxa in a faunal assemblage (Kintigh 1989). Ideally, species richness would be low in the Beacon Island assemblage, reflecting the few introduced and native species available for consumption, and high in the West Wallabi Island assemblage where the survivors subsisted on a variety of native fauna. However, the great differences in sample size between the two assemblages may influence the correlations of richness to sample size, because richness can be tightly correlated to sample size (Grayson 1984:132; Plog and Hegmon 1993:489).

The predicted richness observations are influenced by a variety of variables that may obscure the archaeological visibility of the assemblage differences created by the *Batavia* crisis. There are at least four variables that influence the relationship of species richness and sample size: the taphonomic history of the assemblages (Schmitt and Lupo 1995); the quality of the recovery techniques; the sample size; and the total species richness of each island. If there is no significant correlation between sample size and richness, then these four variables were probably not significant influences on the difference in richness between the two assemblages. A significant correlation between sample size and richness can be controlled by the gradual removal of analytic units with small numbers of members (Jones, Beck and Grayson 1989). This method is not used here because of the lack of details for the 1967 excavation units.

The limitations imposed by the lack of excavation records allow the demonstration of the effects of sample size on richness but preclude the reduction of these effects. If species richness is significantly related to sample size for both assemblages, then differences observed in species richness may be a function of sample size, and not reflect the *Batavia* survivors' subsistence behaviours.

Identification

One of the first steps in interpreting the diet of the survivors is establishing the identity of the animals represented by the faunal assemblages. This required the identification animals represented by specimens (pieces of bone). Animals known not to be native to the Abrolhos Islands or carried abroad the *Batavia* (for example, a dog or grey kangaroo) were assumed to represent post-*Batavia* occupational history.

Specimens and elements (whole bones) were identified using comparative collections at the Centre for Archaeology and the Zoology Department at the University of Western Australia, the Anatomy Museum at the Murdoch University School of Veterinary Sciences and the Western Australian Museum. Native mammals (tamar, other macropods, native rat and sea lion) were identified the using collections at the Centre for Archaeology and the Zoology Department at the University of Western Australia. The Murdoch reference collection included domestic mammals such as sheep, goat, pig, horse, cow, dog and smaller non-native mammals. Illustrated books on faunal analysis also assisted in the identification of bones. These books include Amorosi (1989) Schmid (1972), Merrilees and Porter (1979), Walker (1985), Wheeler and Jones (1989) and Barnett (1978).

Mammal bones were easily differentiated from fish and bird bones by their mass, texture and structure. Mammal bones are generally heavier, thicker and more solid than fish and bird bones. The *Batavia* was probably carrying pig bones in the form of barrelled pork and live pigs (Green 1977:375-376; Bruijn et al. 1987:214-218). The more recent guano mining and crayfishing populations introduced cows, horses, goats, sheep and smaller non-native mammals to the Wallabi Group (Storr 1965).

Fish bones were isolated by their comparative lightness and fibrous or 'woody' appearance, and their distinctive shape and structure. In archaeological contexts a fish bone is commonly either a vertebrae, scale, fin bone, head bone or otolith (Wheeler and Jones 1989:79-120). A total of 389 fish species are listed for the Abrolhos (Hatcher 1984), although when W. B. Alexander visited in 1913, he considered only four families to be good eating and in sufficient abundance to be reliable food source (Alexander 1922). The modern classifications of these are: *Lethrinidae* species, *Sparidae* species, *Labridae* species and *Scaridae* species (figure 2.4). Pelsaert states that 'hereabout, it is very rich in fish, three kinds of fish but they are quite different in taste and shape than on other

coasts' with no further details (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:235). Because of limited time and resources, this project expended more effort on identifying these four families than historically less represented fish. Samples of *Sparidae*, *Lethrinidae*, and *Scaridae* from Shark Bay were obtained from the Fisheries Department of Western Australia and skeletal reference collections were prepared after the procedures in Wheeler and Jones (1989) and Abel (1995). The photographic reference collection in Barnett (1978) provided identifications for other fish species.

Bird taxa are abundant on the Abrolhos Islands. Ninety-five bird species were recorded for the Abrolhos Islands and adjacent reef areas over the period 1845 to 1983, with four species (Wedge-tailed Shearwater, Little Shearwater, White-breasted Sea Eagle and the Pied Cormorant) nesting in large numbers in the Wallabi Group (figure 2.4, Storr, Johnstone and Griffin 1986). Pelsaert mentions 'grey turtledoves' (probably Brush Bronzewing) and the predicator records fowls on the islands (probably Shearwaters) and an abundance of eggs on West Wallabi Island (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:236; Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:267). The Ornithology Department at the Western Australian Museum has skeletons of two of species recorded in recent times (Little Shearwater and Pied Cormorant). Other bird bone was identified using skeletons of birds within the same family in the Museum collection. For example, the White-breasted Sea Eagle (Accipitridae *Haliaeetus leucogaster*) was identified by comparison to other birds of the Accipitridae family. The limited comparative material restricted the number of identifiable bird and fish bones to a few abundant species and resulted in a large number of unidentified bird bones.

Quantification

There is a vast and increasing body of literature devoted to finding the most accurate and appropriate measures of abundance of archaeological fauna (for example, Gautier 1984; Brewer 1992; Ringrose 1993; Lyman 1994b). In this study, three common measures were employed; number of identified specimens (NISP), minimum number of individuals (MNI) and bone mass. The NISP, MNI and mass were compared within each taxon to see if significant differences exist in the proportions of species between the Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island. Calculating differences in proportions mitigates the great differences in sample sizes of the two assemblages, which make the

individual comparison of actual NISP, MNI and bone mass values inappropriate (Gifford-Gonzalez 1991).

Historical data on the *Batavia* insurrection suggests the survivors divided into two groups that were separated from each other and their interactions were hostile. The group on Beacon Island, consisting of sailors and passengers, were close to the wreck and according to the historical data subsisted on salvaged supplies and the limited native fauna. The historical data indicates that the group on West Wallabi Island, mainly soldiers and later also passengers and sailors, subsisted entirely on the abundant native fauna. If the archaeological record is representative of the historical data and the historical data is reliable, then the West Wallabi Island assemblage will have a higher proportion of native taxa than Beacon Island, and the Beacon Island assemblage will have a higher proportion of salvaged taxa than the West Wallabi Island assemblage.

The three different abundance measurements (NISP, MNI, bone mass) are used because they each provided unique information about the sample (Brewer 1992:217). MNI and NISP provide ordinal level data that gives information on ranked abundance (Grayson 1984:93-96; Brewer 1992:214-215). MNI is a measure of the relative abundance of different species while NISP is useful as an indicator of the degree of diversity in faunal exploitation (Crabtree 1985:76-77). Ordinal level data reveals which of the two islands has a higher rank of native or introduced animals, but does not measure the differences (Brewer 1992:209). In this case, ordinal data is sufficient because only the ranked proportions of fauna were considered. Bone mass provides ratio level data where differences in abundances can be measured. The use of the three measurements provided a broader, more reliable understanding of the assemblage.

NISP is an observational unit defined as the number of identified specimens per taxon and is frequently converted to a percentage (Grayson 1979:201; 1984:17). Although NISP is easy to calculate and popular as an abundance measure, it is the most heavily criticised of all units of abundance measurement (Grayson 1979:201). Some of the criticisms of NISP include: the unit is affected by butchering patterns; numbers of identified specimens vary from species to species; it assumes all specimens are equally affected by taphonomic and post-depositional processes; the unit may be affected by recovery techniques; finds of entire skeletons may skew abundance counts; and it is

affected by the problem of interdependence, namely, having no way of knowing if two bones necessarily come from different animals (Grayson 1979:201; 1984:20-24). The problem of interdependence associated with NISP is partially mitigated by including MNI as an abundance measure.

MNI is an analytical unit calculated by determining the minimum number of individuals necessary to account for all the skeletal material identified for a taxon within a set of faunal remains (Grayson 1979:203). In practice, MNI figures are typically compiled by finding the most abundant element of a taxon, separating it into right and left components and using the greater number as the result (Brewer 1992:211; White 1953). The method of calculating MNI is not seriously affected by different taxa having different numbers of bones or differential butchering (where either the whole carcass or only part of it is in the assemblage). Compared to NISP, the MNI method is relatively insensitive to differential fragmentation between species (Klein and Cruz-Uribe 1984:26). The MNI count however, is at least as sensitive as NISP to the effects of fragmentation on the entire sample. As the sample becomes more fragmented, less elements can be identified, resulting in a low MNI count. In highly fragmented assemblages NISP may be a more representative abundance measure than MNI (Grayson 1978; Marshall and Pilgram 1993). Other problems with MNI are that it tends to exaggerate the abundance of rarer taxa in the sample (Payne 1972), and small sample sizes seem to have an exaggerating effect on minimum numbers (Grayson 1978).

MNI could be used as a ratio scale except for the restrictive assumption that the faunal specimens were distributed equally over the archaeological site (Brewer 1992:212). This assumption is almost never true, so it is appropriate to use MNI as an ordinal scale only. Chaplin (1971) and Grayson (1979:204-221) show that MNI values vary depending on how the faunal remains have been analytically aggregated, with the true minimum number obtained when the entire site is treated as a single unit. The absence of excavation details for the majority of the Beacon Island sample required the entire assemblage to be treated as a single analytical unit. For the purposes of quantification in this thesis, the total sample from each island was treated as an analytical unit, making up the two units. One unit is Beacon Island, combining the unprovenanced 1967 material and the 1974 material, and the other unit is the 1974 material from West Wallabi Island. Using only two units minimised problems of aggregation and the unequal distribution of most abundant elements across the site, meaning the MNI value approaches a true minimum number (Brewer 1992:213). Some

researchers calculate MNI on the basis of age and sex (Bokonyi 1970:291) and apply it to separate stratigraphic zones and features of a site (Flannery 1967; Perkins and Daly 1968). The lack of information on recovery of the faunal remains precluded calculating MNI by stratigraphic zones, and it was not possible to establish age and sex of the faunal material with the available time and reference collections.

Binford (1977:69-72; 1984:50-51) and Lyman (1979) have argued that MNI and NISP are inappropriate for quantifying archaeologically derived faunal remains in human behavioural terms. Binford (1984:50-51) proposed a 'behaviourally oriented' alternative to MNI by attempting to explain the variation in frequencies of skeletal parts recovered from archaeological sites, which he believes are more representative of human behaviour. Binford's minimum number of animal units (MAU) is defined as the number of identified specimens divided by the number of times that part occurs in the skeleton of the identified animal. Minimum animal units are recorded with the modified general utility index (MGUI), which is a relative scale that assesses amounts of meat, marrow and grease associated with the skeletal elements measured in the MAU (Binford 1978; 1981; 1984). The MAU% is plotted against MGUI values, providing a set of curves inferred to demonstrate different animal utilisation strategies. A 'gourmet' strategy is suggested when parts of high utility (for example; from a habitation site) only are recovered, versus a reverse utility site where elements of low utility were recovered (for example, a kill or butchery site). At reverse utility sites high utility elements were assumed to have been transported away from the site (Binford 1978:69-72).

Binford's utilisation strategy measurements could be very useful in zooarchaeology if the assumptions used to produce and interpret the curves were in fact a reflection of human decision-making processes. It is difficult to sustain assumptions of the uses of fauna being uniform and dependent of their utility indexes when assemblages have complex (and often unknown) taphonomic histories and when human behavioural processes other than instant optimisation of economic return are involved. Lyman (1985) observed that many of the bones that rank high on the economic utility index (MGUI) rank low in bone density, while many that rank low on the MGUI have a high density. This means that post-depositional forces can cause an inverse correlation between MGUI and MAU%. The inverse correlation is caused by bones that rank highly on the MGUI index being more susceptible to fragmentation than low ranking MGUI bones and thus becoming unidentifiable (Grayson 1989;

Lyman and O'Brien 1987). Binford was aware of the problem of fragmentation and substituted MAU for the minimum number of elements (MNE), derived by counting all the distal and proximal portions and using the most abundant count as the MNE value (Binford 1977:70). However, the MNE count is weakened by the same flaws as MNI, being susceptible to the aggregative methods employed in excavation and analysis (Brewer 1992:221).

Like Binford, Lyman (1979) argues that it is illogical to assume that entire animals are consumed if entire animals are not represented in the sample. He proposed a new technique based on identifying and quantifying butchering units, defined as the 'piece[s] of the animal body that results from the act of butchering' (Lyman 1979:539). The strength of this method is its focus on providing an accurate estimate of consumed meat, and therefore more accurate calculations of food energy values. Piper (1991:271-285) acknowledges Lyman's approach to butchery analysis, but says the method should be rejected because it does not account for functional, cultural and individual variation of butchery methods in the archaeological sample. According to Piper (1991:271-286), Lyman's method assumes that meat consumption is of the primary butchery units (such as the division of the carcass into two or more units), when meat consumption is actually of secondary units (for example; archaeologically invisible deboned cuts). Further problems with Lyman's method stem from it being a refinement of the MNI method, and therefore suffers (like Binford's MAU and MNE) from the MNI problems of differential preservation, sample size and aggregation (Piper 1991:52).

As Binford and Lyman demonstrate, MNI and NISP can be converted into meat mass via derived units such as MAE, MNE and butchery units, but none of these overcome the problems of cultural biases on what determines useable meat, troublesome taphonomic histories and the weaknesses of MNI and NISP. Bone mass can be converted into meat mass using a method which avoids the problems of MNI and NISP, but the relationship between bone and meat mass can not be described by a simple or constant formula (Casteel 1978; Grayson 1984:172). Allometric formulae can be used to provide a biologically based derivation of an accurate estimation of edible meat mass (Reitz, Quitmyer, Hale, Scudder and Wing 1987). Unfortunately these formulae are complex and require biological information (body mass/age ratios) that is not available for some fauna of the Abrolhos Islands. The allometric method is also affected by fragmentation and butchering factors that influence the number of elements able to be used in the allometric formulae (Lyman 1979; Piper 1991:50; Jackson 1989).

Edible meat mass is a highly appropriate measure for subsistence studies because it relates directly to consumption but is difficult to calculate, requiring knowledge of butchering patterns and biological data for the fauna. In this study, calculation of meat mass was avoided because of the difficulties involved, and because each carcass cannot be assumed to have been treated the same. Butchering techniques may have varied according to species, size, purpose, distance from camp, and who was performing the butchery. Bone mass is used here as another approach to the measurement of the relative proportions of species within and between the two assemblages.

Butchery

Butchery practises, although problematic for quantification, have received attention as an indicator of culturally prescribed patterns of consumption and distribution. Butchery patterns are defined as 'a set or series of activities that are directed towards the extraction of consumable resources from an animal carcass' (Lynam 1987a:252). Butchery patterns can be used to suggest what portions of animals were consumed by the *Batavia* survivors, if they shared food amongst themselves (cf. Binford 1984) and how different species were butchered (for example, if there is a difference in butchery patterns between native and introduced species)

To record data on butchery, a system of five types of butchery marks (described in table 4.1) was used in this research, based on Crader (1990). The butchery type, the mark placement, orientation, length and depth were recorded. Butchery data and documentary data of the *Batavia* survivors were compared to reconstruct the butchery patterns of the survivors.

Butchery type	Description
Cut	Straight, narrow incised lines probably made with a sharp tool
Chop	Wider than cut marks where a small wedge of bone was removed
Scrape	Shallow layer of surface bone has been removed, leaving striations
Shear	Straight-walled planar surfaces where the bone has been split apart
Saw	Flat surface of bone with regular parallel striations and saw teeth marks

Table 4.1
System for identification and recording of butchery marks after Crader (1990)

The identification of butchery patterns is limited by sample size, extent of fragmentation and variation in butchery practises. For assessing butchery patterns, a low sample size has the same problem as a highly fragmented assemblage: the elements exhibiting butchery marks are archaeologically invisible because they either are not included in the sample or too fragmented to be analytically useful. A small sample (such as from West Wallabi Island) may contain insufficient numbers of butchered specimens to infer a pattern. Variability in butchery behaviour also reduces the possibility of identifying a pattern in small assemblages (Piper 1991:289-294).

In the context of the *Batavia* survivors the visibility of butchered meat is a significant concern. Crader (1984; 1990) and Gurlday (1977) have argued that meat stored in barrels leaves no archaeological trace. Their research suggests that salted meat was deboned during butchering so the meat could be stored in barrels (Crader 1984; 1990; Gurlday 1977). The deboning process makes salted meat archaeologically invisible and would distort reconstructed butchery patterns (Crader 1990:713). However, in an analysis of barrelled meat from a nineteenth-century shipwreck, English (1991) shows that barrelled salted meats are archaeologically visible, and can provide information of specific methods of butchery. Underwater excavations at the *Batavia* and the *Vergulde Draeck* wreck sites have recovered butchered bones of animals recorded in the seventeenth-century catalogue of provisions (Stanbury 1975:47; Green 1977; Bruin et al. 1987:214-218). If the *Batavia* survivors consumed meat salvaged from the wreck, then the archaeological record should include a butchery pattern consistent with seventeenth-century barrelled meat.

Burning

Cooking, like butchering, is an important step in the preparation of food for consumption. Further insight into the subsistence behaviours of the *Batavia* survivors is possible by identifying burnt bone. It was possible to see if bones were burnt and if there was any relationship to species (for example, introduced or native) or assemblage (that is, if one group burnt more bones than the other). No bushfires have been recorded on West Wallabi Island or Beacon Island (Nardi 1998), so all burnt bone in this study are assumed to result from consumption-related human activity. Bone may be intentionally burnt by humans during cooking, for disposal of waste and as fuel for fires (David 1990; James 1989; Balme 1980). Johnson (1989:441) records four stages in the

burning of bone, with each stage occurring at a different temperature and giving the bone a different colour. In this study, only the presence or absence of any of Johnson's four stages was recorded.

Completeness

While butchery and burning are assumed to result from human activity, bones can be modified in other ways by various human and non-human processes. In this thesis 'completeness' is a measure of how much of an element is represented by a specimen. The completeness of a bone is affected by human utilisation, such as breaking, and post-depositional destruction. Methods of describing completeness include to ratio of NISP/MNI and Marean's (1991) completeness index. For this study, Landon's (1996:137) percent present system is used. For non-limb bones, completeness was recorded as 'whole' or by the quarters remaining of the whole. Often a brief description of the specimen was included, such as '1/4 maxilla with tooth row'. The fraction of the specimen present expresses a range rather than a discrete value; 1/4 is less than or equal to one-quarter of the whole element, 2/4 is one-quarter to a half of the whole, 3/4 is half or more (but not all) of the whole element (Landon 1996:137). Completeness of limb bones was described similarly, with the added details of the missing ends (proximal, distal or both) of the bone.

Eight types of long bone fracture types were recorded based on Marshall (1989) (figure 4.1). Fractures can be caused by antemortem processes (living animals breaking their bones), scavengers feeding on the bones, post-depositional processes (trampling, crushing, other taphonomic processes) and human activity. When fracturing patterns occurs with other signs of human consumption (such as burnt bone, butchered bone, or bone of taxa presumed to be preferred for eating) then that fracturing pattern could be assumed to be a result of human modification (Lyman 1994a:324-338; Johnson 1985:175). Where there is no relationship between fracturing patterns and signs of human consumption, the pattern could result from non-human post-depositional processes.

Figure 4.1
Schematic illustrations of fracture types after Marshall (1989), from Lyman (1994a)

Weathering

The primary purpose of recording weathering was to identify and exclude specimens deposited in post-*Batavia* events. In this context, weathering is defined as 'the process by which the original microscopic organic and inorganic components of bone are separated from each other and destroyed by physical and chemical agents operating on the bone *in situ*, either on the surface or within the soil zone' (Behrensmeyer 1978:153). The process of weathering reflects the passing of time (Lyman and Fox 1989), so it is assumed that a specimen displaying an advanced weathering stage has been exposed to weathering for longer than a less weathered specimen (Lyman 1994a:345-375).

The relationship between weathering stage and duration of exposure is not direct or constant because other factors influence weathering, such as variations in bone density between skeletal elements and taxa, depositional microenvironments and soil matrix microenvironments (Lyman and Fox 1989; Lyman 1994a:361-636). Ideally, information on duration of bone exposure would be derived from data on weathering combined with data on the extent of bone dispersal, gnawing damage to bones, disarticulation, bone breakage and destruction (Lyman and Fox 1989:314). The limitations in stratigraphic control over the assemblages used and in available time for analysis confine duration data to weathering stages.

A five-stage system based on Behrensmeyer (1978), Voigt (1983) and Johnson (1985) was used for identifying and recording the degree of weathering of a specimen (table 4.2). In this thesis the third weathering stage was arbitrarily made the stage indicating a date of deposition contemporary with the *Batavia* survivors. The use of weathering stages to estimate duration of exposure is problematic, so this method of isolating the *Batavia* survivors' faunal remains was used only in combination with other methods, such as the exclusion of taxa introduced to the islands after the departure of the *Batavia* survivors.

Weathering Stage	Stage Name	Description
1	Initial weathering	Soft tissue gone, fine splits appear parallel to fibre structure
2	Slight weathering	flaking of outer surface, shallow cracks present
3	Light weathering	fibrous texture, extensive flaking, rounded crack edges
4	Medium weathering	coarsely fibrous and rough surface, deep open cracks
5	Heavy weathering	soft powdery texture, very fragile

Table 4.2
System of identification and recording of weathering stages after Behrensmeyer (1978), Voigt (1983) and Johnson (1985)

Chapter Five Results and Analysis

Introduction

It has been asserted that 'in order for zooarchaeologists to properly assess the faunal sample, they must know the recovery methods' (Jolley 1983:67; cf. Zeigler 1973:3). Two analytic units formed the basis of this investigation, the faunal assemblages from the 1967 and 1974 excavations of Beacon Island and the faunal assemblage from the 1974 excavations of West Wallabi Island. The analysis undertaken in this project was limited by the recovery methods, especially the absence of comprehensive details for the recovery methods for 91% of the bone specimens. Nevertheless, this chapter shows that even with limited detail on recovery methods it was possible to determine the proportions of species represented in the sample, the correlation of sample size to richness, traces of butchery patterns and patterns of burnt, fragmented and fractured bone. The weathering stages of the bones were discussed where the exclusion of less weathered (and assumed younger) bone has a significant implication for the analysis.

Correlation of Richness and Sample Size

Based on data in the historical sources treated in chapter two, it was predicted that the survivors on West Wallabi Island had a more diverse diet than survivors on Beacon Island. The predicant and the author of the first Leyden Ferry-boat letter both suggest birds, fish, tammars and possibly sea lions in great abundance on West Wallabi Island. This is a striking contrast to Beacon Island, where the predicant reportedly ate grass to survive (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:267) and the letter author says they lived on what came drifting from the ship (Stow 1972:8). Differences in the species diversity between the two islands would lead one to expect a higher species richness on West Wallabi Island than Beacon Island. Table 5.1 shows the observed species richness and sample sizes for each island. Although it is clear that the Beacon Island sample size is an order of magnitude greater than the West Wallabi sample, the correspondence to species richness is not so marked. The chi-squared value is 33.4, significant at the 0.001

level, indicating a significant association between richness and sample size (see appendix B). After consideration of the sample sizes, the strength of the association was found to be very weak, as illustrated by the Cramer's V^2 value of 0.008 (where zero indicates no relationship).

	Beacon	West Wallabi
richness	22	13
sample size (NISP)	3436	334

Table 5.1
Species richness and sample size of Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island

These results show that the predictions derived from the historic sources about the relationship between sample size and species richness do not hold when tested with archaeological data. The Beacon Island assemblage has a higher species richness than the West Wallabi Island assemblage, contrary to predictions of the opposite. However, the strength of association of sample size and richness is very weak, so it is not appropriate to make confident statements about the nature of the relationship between sample size and richness and what variables may have influenced it. If sample size was the main factor acting on richness, a stronger association (for example; a Cramer's V^2 value of >0.5) would be expected. These statistical results suggest that there is a significant relationship between sample size and richness for the two units, but it was not possible to discern why.

The disparity between the two data sets (documentary and archaeological) does not necessarily indicate contradiction. The predicant and letter-author are both assumed to have provided an accurate account of the subsistence resources available on each island. However, they exaggerate the differences between the mutineers and soldiers. Both authors imposed Calvinist morals onto the survivors' situation. They described soldiers and others on West Wallabi as protected and provided for by God because they were good. The mutineers were depicted as evil and consequently suffered a lack of subsistence resources. The evilness of the mutineers is compounded because their actions caused innocent survivors to perish. The structural opposition imposed by the predicant and other author may have biased their descriptions of subsistence resources.

One of the assumptions made here is that the analysed sample represented all species consumed by the *Batavia* survivors. Lyman (1995) has proposed a method for determining when the absence of taxa is due to its actual absence versus sampling deficiencies. The reasons why a taxa might not be found include: it was never present to begin with; the remains did not preserve in the archaeological record; the sampling design was faulty; the recovery techniques were inappropriate or inadequate or the sample sizes were too small (Lyman 1995:374-375). However, Lyman's method requires details about archaeological sampling and recovery that are not available for the Abrolhos data, and uses several sites, where only two were used here. Consequently, it was not possible to apply Lyman's method, and an incontrovertible archaeological explanation of the sample size/richness correlation cannot be offered because of the limited information on recovery methods.

It may be that the sample sizes actually reflect the abundance and richness of animals consumed. The number of survivors on Beacon Island began at about 200, and dropped to about 40 due to deaths from thirst, starvation and illness. The population on West Wallabi began at about 40 and possibly rose to about 50. With more people on Beacon Island than West Wallabi Island (initially), it might be expected that greater amount of faunal remains would be found on Beacon Island. Such speculations are unjustifiable with the limited information about recovery methods and sampling. Therefore it is not possible to demonstrate that differences in population sizes was the source of differences in the sample size and richness of the faunal assemblages.

Identification and Quantification

Introduced Mammals

The four main taxa of introduced species identified here are sheep and/or goat, cow, pig and horse (figure 5.2). Documentary records suggest pig and cow were carried by the *Batavia* and sheep/goat and horse were not related to the period of the *Batavia* survivors' occupation. The bone were identified to genus level only (*Ovis/Capra*, *Sus*, *Equus*, and *Bos*) because of the limited reference collection and time available for identification. The difficulties in differentiating post-cranial sheep and goat bone were acknowledged by combining the two into one taxonomic category. In the Beacon Island assemblage, sheep/goat, cow, pig and horse were identified. Numerous macropod bones was identified on Beacon Island and assumed to be introduced because the size

of identified elements and specimens were larger than the range of skeletal material of the tammar. In the West Wallabi Island assemblage only pig and sheep/goat were identified. In the Beacon Island assemblage and the West Wallabi Island assemblage unidentified introduced mammal bone was found. Bone classified as 'unidentified' introduced bone is bone that has a mammalian shape, texture and structure that is different from the dense spongy bone of the sea lion and is too large for tammar. No introduced small mammals (such as cats, rabbits or dogs) were identified in the assemblages.

	Beacon						West Wallabi					
	NISP		MNI		Mass		NISP		MNI		Mass	
	N	%	N	%	g	%	N	%	N	%	g	%
Pig	26	0.76	1	0.47	377.7	4.2	2	0.59	1	4.34	17.65	4.45
Sheep/goat	82	2.38	3	1.42	530.69	5.9	1	0.39	1	4.34	5.24	1.32
Cow	34	0.99	1	0.47	1519.5	16.9	0	0	0	0	0	0
Horse	1	0.03	1	0.47	257.71	2.87	0	0	0	0	0	0
Macropod	9	0.26	1	0.47	32.42	0.36	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unknown	60	1.74	0	0	364.07	4.05	2	0.59	0	0	6.53	1.65

Table 5.2

Abundance measures of introduced mammals in assemblages from Beacon and West Wallabi Islands

The sheep and horse bones presumably derive from post-*Batavia* occupation. The horse bone in the Beacon Island assemblage suggests their presence at some time on the island. The use of horses on West Wallabi Island relates to the guano industry as indicated by the railway and horse yards. However, no horse bones were found in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. Sheep and goats were kept as a food source by guano workers and later by people involved in crayfishing (Storr, Johnstone and Griffin 1985:8). The crayfishers also used sheep and cow as bait for their craytraps (Edwards 1966:173). The presence of introduced macropod bone probably results from the use of kangaroo meat as craybait (Stanbury pers. comm. 1999).

In the Beacon Island assemblage the sheep/goat class is most abundant, while pig is most abundant in the West Wallabi Island assemblage, according to NISP, MNI and bone mass measurements (table 5.2). The Beacon Island assemblage has higher NISP, MNI and bone mass values for all classes of introduced mammal than the West Wallabi Island assemblage. Table 5.2 shows the NISP, MNI and bone mass values for introduced mammals on Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island with percentages of

the whole assemblage. Introduced mammals in the Beacon Island assemblage are 6.16% (NISP), 2.83% (MNI) and 34.28% (mass) of the Beacon Island assemblage. The high representation by mass on Beacon Island is in part due to large mammal bone (such as horse and cow) being heavier and denser than bones of other types of animals. For the West Wallabi Island assemblage, introduced mammals make up 1.57% (NISP), 8.68% (MNI) and 7.42% (mass) of the island's assemblage. The West Wallabi Island assemblage has no cow or horse bone, which contributes to the percentage mass being not as high as the Beacon Island assemblage.

Historical data on provisions carried by VOC ships suggest pork (live and barrelled) and possibly barrelled beef were the two types of meat carried and consumed on the *Batavia*, neither of which are represented highly in either assemblage (Green 1977:375-376, Bruijn, Gaastra and Schoffer 1987:214-218). The percentage of pig and cow combined in the Beacon Island assemblage is 1.75% (NISP), 0.94% (MNI), 21.1% (mass); and in the West Wallabi Island assemblage 0.59% (NISP), 4.34% (MNI) and 4.45% (mass). The Beacon Island assemblage has a higher proportion of pig and cow than the West Wallabi Island assemblage, according to %NISP and %mass. The higher %MNI in the West Wallabi assemblage is caused by the small sample size: the %MNI represents only one bone. Also, the high level of fragmentation of pig and cow specimens in the Beacon Island assemblage reduces the %MNI. The %MNI is reduced in highly fragmented assemblages because there are fewer bones that can be identified and sided to generate an MNI value.

It is interesting to note that previous studies have recorded variations within species of introduced fauna recovered from the *Batavia* wreck. Merrilees (1970) and Boessneck (1971) recognise two different types of pig species in bones recovered during excavations of the *Batavia* wreck. They identify a regular domesticated variety and a 'rangier breed' possibly representing wild pig from southern Africa, taken on when the ship stopped to collect provisions (Merrilees 1970). Inter-species variation was not recorded in this project because of limitations in comparative material and time. Introduced mammal bones are not mentioned in the records of the Aquinas excavations of the stone structure at Slaughter Point on West Wallabi Island (O'Loughlin 1964; 1965).

Native Mammals

The tammar and sea lion are the two main native mammal species on the islands. Although the tammar is today found living only on East and West Wallabi Islands, its skeletal remains were also identified in the Beacon Island assemblage. Both islands' assemblages contained tammar and sea lion bones, and in the West Wallabi Island assemblage native rat bones were also identified. Specimens were determined 'unknown' where it was not possible to discern between the three species. The Aquinas excavations also found sea lion and tammar bones on West Wallabi Island at the Slaughter Point structure, but provided no details on quantity (O'Loughlin 1964; 1965).

While all three native mammals have been recorded on West Wallabi Island, only sea lions have been recorded on Beacon Island. The find of tammar bone on Beacon Island indicates that transfer of fauna has taken place between Beacon Island and one or both of East and West Wallabi Island. Sampling the assemblages by excluding less weathered bone (assumed to be post-*Batavia*) showed the possibility that tammars bones were on Beacon Island during the time the survivors were there. Therefore, transfer could have taken place during the time the *Batavia* survivors were on the islands, or during subsequent occupations by others. Later occupants, including explorers and crayfishers, presumably used tammars as a food source and bait.

	Beacon						West Wallabi					
	NISP		MNI		Mass		NISP		MNI		Mass	
	N	%	N	%	g	%	N	%	N	%	g	%
Tammar	145	4.22	6	2.84	323.1	3.59	86	25.75	4	17.4	192.38	48.57
Sea lion	101	2.94	4	1.89	2014.68	22.41	0	0	0	0	0	0
Native rat	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.59	1	4.35	0.39	0.098
Unknown	5	0.14	0	0	7.1	0.08	9	2.69	0	0	3.65	0.922

Table 5.3
Abundance measures of native mammals in assemblages from Beacon and West Wallabi Islands

Of the three native mammals identified, the tammar is most frequently represented in both assemblages as shown in table 5.3. The high proportion (22%) of sea lion bone mass on Beacon Island is potentially due to the high density of sea lion bone. No sea lion bone was found in the West Wallabi Island assemblage, contrary to predictions made from the documentary sources. It is possible that the survivors on West Wallabi Island consumed and disposed of sea lion bone away from the excavated areas in and around the Slaughter Point structure. The survivors may have attempted

to keep the structure relatively clean and hygienic by consuming and disposing large and greasy sea lion bones elsewhere. Alternatively, because of the size and mass of a sea lion relative to tammars, birds and fish, the survivors may have minimised energy expenditure by processing sea lions at the kill site. If this was the case, only edible parts of the sea lion would be transported back to the structure, leaving only a negligible trace of sea lion in the archaeological record.

The West Wallabi Island assemblage has a greater proportion of tammars than the Beacon Island assemblage according to all three abundance measures. In the West Wallabi Island assemblage tammars represent 25.8% (NISP), 17.4% (MNI) and 48.6% (mass) of the whole. It is the most represented taxa in the West Wallabi Island assemblage by NISP and mass. In the Beacon Island assemblage, the proportional abundance measures of tammars are 4.22% (NISP), 2.84% (MNI) and 3.59% (mass). Bones of sea lions are 2.93% (NISP), 1.89% (MNI) and 22.4% (mass) of the Beacon Island assemblage. The proportions of sea lion in the Beacon Island assemblage are similar to the pig/cow class, with comparatively low %NISP and %MNI values and a high %mass. The relatively high %mass corresponds to the large size and high density of bone of large mammals. The two specimens of native rat in the West Wallabi Island assemblage are assumed to be of little significance to the *Batavia* survivors' subsistence behaviours given the high proportion of tammars on West Wallabi Island.

Fish

Six families of fish were identified (Labridae, Scaridae, Sparidae, Lethrinidae, Serranidae and Scombridae), with only Sparidae and Scaridae identified to species level (Sparidae *Pagrus auratus* and Scaridae *Scarus rubroviolaceus*). All families were identified in the Beacon Island assemblage. Only two families (Scaridae and Sparidae) were identified in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. Fragments, specimens and elements that could not be identified with comparative collections were classed as 'unidentified'.

Both islands have equal access to fish in terms of nearby well-stocked reefs. Documentary data indicates that both groups consumed fish and that the survivors on Beacon Island used a small boat and floating wreckage to 'fish' near the wreck while the survivors on West Wallabi Island were restricted to the shores. However, Pelsaert's journal suggests that the term 'fishing' refers to their retrieving goods from the wreck, not necessarily catching fish to eat (Pelsaert in Drake-Brockman 1963:134, 145, 146, 150, 151, 153, 220, 221). The documentary sources are not equivocal about a link between

fishing for fish and the possession of a boat. Therefore, the documentary data does not provide evidence that the difference in fish bones between the two assemblages results exclusively from the use of a boat.

The availability of fishing equipment, such as hooks, may have influenced the amount of fish caught on West Wallabi Island. The Aquinas excavations to West Wallabi Island reported no fish bones at the Slaughter Point structure, but found some bent iron fragments and suggested that they might be fish hooks (O'Loughlin 1965:12; 1966:12). The improvised fish hooks found by Aquinas College might represent an attempt by the survivors to exploit new sources of subsistence as the population increased and other resources depleted (Bevacqua 1974c:17). The absence of fish remains at the site suggest this was an unsuccessful adaptation, or that the survivors threw the remains in the water or elsewhere on the island (cf. Colley 1990). Even if the West Wallabi group unequivocally possessed fishing equipment, the abundance of other fauna (such as tammars, sea lions and birds) may have reduced their reliance on fish as a food source. In contrast, the survivors on Beacon Island relied heavily on fish because it was an important subsistence resource in the absence of abundant tammars.

	Beacon						West Wallabi					
	NISP		MNI		Mass		NISP		MNI		Mass	
	N	%	N	%	g	%	N	%	N	%	g	%
Labridae	48	1.39	13	6.161	60.04	0.67	0	0	0	0	0	0
Scaridae	243	7.07	66	31.28	129.91	1.44	1	0.29	1	4.35	0.08	0.02
Sparidae	309	8.99	34	16.11	1300.26	14.4	12	3.59	1	4.35	18.54	4.68
Lethrinidae	5	0.14	1	0.47	4.23	0.05	0	0	0	0	0	0
Serranidae	13	0.37	5	2.37	66.5	0.74	0	0	0	0	0	0
Scombridae	2	0.06	1	0.47	1.01	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unknowns	1692	49.2	30	14.22	1246.78	13.87	6	1.79	0	0	10.21	2.58

Table 5.4
Abundance measures of fish in assemblages from Beacon and West Wallabi Islands

In the Beacon Island assemblage fish rank highly according to NISP and MNI abundance measures. Table 5.4 shows the abundance measures for fish. Total combined identified fish proportions in the Beacon Island assemblage are: 18.02% (NISP), 56.87% (MNI) and 17.31% (mass). These are the highest NISP and MNI values for all classes of identified taxa on Beacon Island. The high MNI value for fish in the Beacon Island assemblage results from the way fish are represented in the archaeological record. In

the Beacon Island assemblage fish are represented by vertebrae and head bones because these are some of the most durable bones in a fish skeleton (Wheeler and Jones 1989:87-125; Colley 1990).

Fish head bones were relatively easy to identify and quantify using comparative skeletal material. Even where it was not possible to identify the species the bone represents, it was possible to include it in the MNI count. For example, several fish skulls could not be identified with the available comparative resources, but clearly represented at least one fish (per skull) present in the assemblage. These unidentified skulls would be excluded if identified specimens only were used in the MNI count. Specimens that represented unidentified fish species were included in the MNI count to give a more realistic representation of the sample, resulting in a high %MNI. The differences in quantification measures are also affected by the level of fragmentation in the assemblages, which are low for fish in the Beacon Island assemblage, favouring the representation of whole bones.

Birds

Six families of bird were identified: Diomedeidae, Procellariidae, Phalacrocoracidae, Accipitridae, Falconidae, Scolopacidae, and Laridae; and from these three genus were identified: Procellariidae *Puffinus* species (Shearwater) and *Pterodroma* species, (Petrel) Phalacrocoracidae *Phalacrocorax* species (Cormorant) and Accipitridae *Haliaeetus* species (Sea Eagle). All families except Falconidae were identified in the Beacon Island assemblage (table 5.5). Petrel bones were not found in the Beacon Island assemblage. In the West Wallabi Island assemblage four families were identified: Accipitridae, Falconidae, Phalacrocoracidae and Procellariidae. Genus identified in the West Wallabi Island assemblage were Cormorant, Shearwater and Petrel. No Sea Eagle bones were found in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. The shearwater found on Beacon Island is assumed to be *Puffinus assimilus* or Little Shearwater and on West Wallabi Island *Puffinus pacificus* or Wedge-tailed Shearwater, based on the reports of Storr, Johnstone and Griffin (1986:18). The 'Accipit/Falco' class represents specimens where it was not possible to determine what family the bone represented. The absence of any Columbidae specimens in the Western Australian Museum collection prevented the identification of any *Phaps elegans* (Brush Bronzewing), the species mentioned by Pelsaert. In retrospect I believe that I probably mistakenly classified Columbidae specimens as Procellariidae. Bird bones identified by their thin, light and hollow appearance that could not be assigned to taxa were described as 'unknown'.

	Beacon						West Wallabi					
	NISP		MNI		Mass		NISP		MNI		Mass	
	N	%	N	%	g	%	N	%	N	%	g	%
Accipitridae	10	0.29	1	0.47	13.21	0.15	7	2.1	2	8.7	11.27	2.85
Accip/Falco	7	0.2	2	0.95	30.13	0.34	1	0.3	1	4.35	2.06	0.52
Falconidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1.2	1	4.35	7.83	1.98
Diomedeidae	1	0.03	1	0.47	3.93	0.04	0	0	0	0	0	0
Procellariidae	58	1.69	7	3.32	51.33	0.57	4	1.2	2	8.7	14.05	3.55
Scolopacidae	1	0.03	1	0.47	0.22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Laridae	7	0.2	2	0.95	6.27	0.07	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sea Eagle	2	0.06	2	0.95	8.39	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cormorant	4	0.12	1	0.47	11.29	0.13	1	0.3	1	4.35	4.49	1.13
Shearwater	156	4.54	16	7.58	41.73	0.46	56	16.8	6	26.1	28.28	7.19
Petrel	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1.2	1	4.35	5.73	1.45
Unknown	208	6.05	11	5.21	76.26	0.85	86	25.8	0	0	39.34	9.93

Table 5.5

Abundance measures of birds in assemblages from Beacon and West Wallabi Islands

The natural distribution of birds is similar for Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island, so the difference in richness of bird taxa may be a result of the factors affecting the correlation of sample size and richness as discussed above. Documentary data indicate that survivors on both islands consumed birds. The vagaries of the recovery details make it difficult to assess what variables specifically affected the consumption and archaeological representation of birds between the two islands, although presumably selectivity may played a role.

Shearwaters are the highest represented taxa in both assemblages, followed by the Procellariidae and Accipitridae families. In the Beacon Island assemblage Shearwaters represent 4.54% (NISP), 7.58% (MNI) and 0.46% (mass) of the whole assemblage. The low %mass is caused by the comparative lightness of bird bones. The Procellariidae family (including specimens not positively identified as Shearwater) is the next most abundant class in the Beacon Island assemblage, at 1.69% (NISP), 3.32% (MNI), and 0.57% (mass) of the assemblage. In the West Wallabi assemblage Shearwaters are 16.8% (NISP), 26.1% (MNI) and 7.19% (mass) of the whole. The Accipitridae family ranks next in abundance in the West Wallabi assemblage consisting of 2.1% (NISP), 8.7% (MNI) and 2.85% (mass) of the assemblage.

The bird remains recovered from Beacon Island are diverse and in small quantities. In the West Wallabi Island assemblage the opposite is true as fewer species are represented but in higher proportions. In the Beacon Island assemblage ten classes of bird are represented, making up 7.16% (NISP), 15.63% (MNI) and 1.85% (mass) of the assemblage. In the West Wallabi assemblage only six classes are represented, making up a higher proportion of the whole than in the Beacon Island assemblage: 23.06% (NISP), 60.87% (MNI) and 18.66% (mass). If the recovery methods and sampling strategies were comparable between the two assemblages, these results suggest an emphasis on a few bird species by the survivors on West Wallabi Island, while survivors on Beacon Island subsisted on a more diverse range of birds without relying heavily on them as a food source.

Unknown bone

Two classes of unknown bone were used: 'unknown mammal' (where it was not possible to distinguish if the bone was from an introduced or native mammal) and 'general unknown' (where the bone was too small and fragmented to contain any useful information about its identity). Both classes of unidentified bone were represented the assemblages from Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island. Table 5.6 shows the distribution of unidentified bones in the different classes by NISP. Fish bones in the Beacon Island assemblage make up the highest proportion of unidentified bones (49.2% NISP) for both assemblages, due mainly to the small comparative collection used in the identification. Bird bone in the West Wallabi assemblage has the next highest proportion of unidentified bone (25.7% NISP), due to their high level of fragmentation.

	Beacon		West Wallabi	
	NISP		NISP	
	N	%	N	%
Introduced mammals	60	1.75	2	0.6
Native mammals	5	0.15	9	2.69
Fish	1692	49.2	6	1.8
Birds	208	6.05	86	25.7
Unknown mammal	163	4.74	38	11.4
Unknown general	44	1.28	12	3.59

Table 5.6
Distribution of unidentified bone across different classes by NISP

The percentages of bone identified to family level (or better) are 36.79% (NISP) in the Beacon Island assemblage and 54.19% (NISP) in the West Wallabi Island

assemblage. Binford and Bertram (1977:125) insist that there 'is no unidentifiable bone' in archaeological assemblages for experienced osteologists. However, I have not had extensive training in osteology and therefore limited in my ability to identify small and fragmented bones. In the context of this study, the concept of 'levels of identifiability' (Klein and Cruz-Urbe 1984:19; Zeigler 1973) is more useful than simply distinguishing between bone identified to taxa and unidentified bone. In this thesis the most relevant categories are not necessarily families or species but the classes of introduced mammal, native mammal, fish and bird (table 5.6). In the Beacon Island assemblage, only 6.02% (NISP) of bone was not identified to a class, and in the West Wallabi Island assemblage, 14.97% (NISP). There is little discussion in the literature on faunal analysis regarding proportion of bones identified and confidence in statements made about the assemblage (cf. Lyman 1982; Brewer 1992; Grayson 1984). The above figures suggest the proportion of identified bone in each assemblage is high (93.98% NISP and 85.03% NISP), and that the sub-sample of identified bone is a realistic representation of the entire assemblage.

Analysis of Proportions of Taxa

A useful comparison for observing differences in subsistence behaviours is the proportion of two groups of taxa, such as the proportion of salvaged and native mammal bones (figure 5.1). Salvaged mammal bones are defined as pork and beef, according to the documentary sources. Tammars, sea lions and native rats are represented as native mammals. The data in figure 5.1 and table 5.6 suggest a high proportion of salvaged to native mammals in the Beacon Island assemblage and a low proportion of salvaged to native mammals in the West Wallabi Island assemblage.

Figure 5.1

Chart showing proportions of introduced and native mammals in the Beacon Island assemblage and the West Wallabi Island assemblage according to NISP, MNI and Mass

	Beacon	West Wallabi
NISP	0.24	0.02
MNI	0.20	0.02
Mass	0.81	0.09

Table 5.7

Table of proportions of introduced and native mammals in the Beacon Island assemblage and the West Wallabi Island assemblage according to NISP, MNI and Mass

To assess if the proportions displayed above were relevant to the *Batavia* survivors they were recalculated with recently deposited bones excluded from the assemblage. Bones weathered to the third, fourth and fifth levels were assumed to represent a duration of exposure equivalent to the time elapsed since the *Batavia* wrecked. Less weathered bones may be the faunal remains of post-*Batavia* occupants such as guano collectors and crayfishers. The differences in proportions of salvaged and native fauna after the more recently deposited bones were excluded are illustrated in figure 5.2 and table 5.8. The relationship of proportions of bones weathered beyond level two (figure 5.2, table 5.8) is similar to the relationship of proportions of all bones (figure 5.1). For each measurement (NISP, MNI and Mass), there is generally an order of magnitude difference between the proportions of salvaged to native fauna on Beacon and West Wallabi Islands.

Figure 5.2

Chart showing proportions of introduced and native mammals for bones weathered beyond level two in the Beacon Island assemblage and the West Wallabi Island assemblage according to NISP, MNI and Mass

	Beacon	West Wallabi
NISP	0.24	0.02
MNI	0.20	0.20
Mass	0.81	0.09

Table 5.8

Table of proportions of introduced and native mammals for bones weathered beyond level two in the Beacon Island assemblage and the West Wallabi Island assemblage according to NISP, MNI and Mass

The consistent difference in proportions between all bones and only the more weathered bones suggests a difference in the survivors' subsistence habits. Native mammals were probably the main mammalian subsistence resource for survivors on West Wallabi Island. In contrast, the survivors on Beacon Island appear to have consumed a higher proportion of mammals salvaged from the ship than native mammals. The relatively low proportion of fish and bird bones (from all weathering stages) in the West Wallabi Island assemblage indicates that native mammals were the probably main source of food (figure 5.3, table 5.9). The archaeological data suggests that compared to bird, a high proportion of fish was consumed on Beacon Island. Information about fish and birds in the documentary sources suggest they were consumed in abundance by survivors on West Wallabi

Island. Emphasis is placed on the abundance of birds and eggs compared to fish on West Wallabi Island in the predicant's account (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:267) and the Leyden Ferry-boat letter (Stow 1972:9). The archaeological record does not reflect an abundant consumption of birds compared to fish on West Wallabi Island, suggesting that waste was disposed away from the stone structures or that details in the documentary sources were exaggerated.

Figure 5.3
Chart showing proportions of fish to bird bones the Beacon Island assemblage and the West Wallabi Island assemblage according to NISP, MNI and Mass

	Beacon	West Wallabi
NISP	5.09	0.12
MNI	3.41	0.14
Mass	11.57	0.26

Table 5.9
Table of proportions of fish to bird bones the Beacon Island assemblage and the West Wallabi Island assemblage according to NISP, MNI and Mass

The identification and quantification analyses suggest the two groups of survivors used different resources, determined by what was available. The survivors on Beacon Island consumed a low proportion of native mammals but a high proportion of salvaged mammals and fish. The survivors on West Wallabi Island relied almost exclusively on native mammals, supplemented by fish and bird.

Butchery Analysis

Introduced Mammals

The rib was the most frequently butchered element on both islands. In the Beacon Island assemblage there are 102 rib specimens in the introduced mammal class, and 36 (35% NISP) exhibit some type of butchery marks (table 5.10). They all indicate a butchery method that divided the ribcage through the antero-posterior plane into two or more units. Beef ribs are the most common, being 33% (NISP) of introduced mammal butchered ribs. The ventral portions of four beef ribs are sawn or sheared at a similar point, suggesting the ribcage was divided into two units. Eight beef rib pieces are shaft fragments with butchery marks at one or both ends, indicating the ribcage was divided into more than two units. There are three butchered sheep/goat ribs with only the dorsal portion present with sawing and shearing visible at both ends. The three pork rib pieces show a similar pattern to sheep/goat ribs, being rib shaft fragments with sawing visible at one or both ends. The butchered ribs of pork and sheep/goat suggest that ribcages were probably divided into three units.

	rib bones		
	total	butchered	
		two units	>2 units
Cow	12	4	4
Sheep/goat	44	0	3
Pig	8	0	3
Unknown	32	3	15

Table 5.10

Butchery patterns for rib bones from introduced mammals in the Beacon Island assemblage

The West Wallabi Island assemblage has one butchered bone, a pork rib shaft with butchery marks at both ends, suggesting the ribcage was divided into more than two units. There were 18 butchered rib bones that could not be identified to genus level in the Beacon Island assemblage. Fifteen of these are shafts with sawn ends, indicating the ribcage was butchered into more than two units. The other three unidentified rib pieces all have an unbutchered end suggesting a division of the ribcage into two units.

Vertebrae of introduced mammal were also frequently found to display butchery marks in the Beacon Island assemblage. Out of 49 vertebrae, 14 (28.57% NISP) were butchered in some way (table 5.11). Six beef vertebrae were sawn to

longitudinally bisect the carcass, and one otherwise intact thoracic vertebra had its neural spine sawn off. Four of the six butchered sheep/goat vertebrae show a pattern of longitudinal bisection of the carcass. The other two sheep/goat vertebrae were sawn transversely, indicating a transverse bisection of part of the carcass to produce a butchered unit. Two unidentified introduced mammal vertebrae displayed signs of butchery, one longitudinally and one laterally.

	vertebrae		
	total	butchered	
		longitudinally	laterally
Cow	12	6	1
Sheep/goat	21	4	2
Pig	8	0	3
Unknown	8	1	1

Table 5.11

Butchery patterns of vertebrae from introduced mammals in the Beacon Island assemblage

Other butchered bone in the Beacon Island assemblage include a two piece conjoin of an unsided sheep/goat tibia that had been sawn in half, the sawn shaft of a horse's right humerus and the distal end of the left humerus of a pig.

Ideally, comparisons would be made with butchery patterns observed in the *Batavia* survivors' assemblages and seventeenth-century Dutch butchery practises. This is hindered by the lack of publications in English describing seventeenth-century Dutch subsistence behaviours. The butchery patterns of introduced mammal rib and vertebrae in the Beacon Island assemblage are consistent with those described by Piper (1991:197-264) for nineteenth century and modern butchery. The pattern of butchery the ribcage into two or more units is also consistent with salted barrelled meat butchery patterns described by English (1991) for nineteenth-century Australia. Other sources contain more general information for comparison with the *Batavia* survivors' assemblages. In an analysis of past consumption patterns, Braudel (1979:197) notes that in the early eighteenth century the diet of the Dutch middle classes and poor consisted of beans, a little salted meat, bread, a small quantity of bacon and very occasionally game. In a study of seventeenth-century Dutch foodways in the United States, Janowitz (1993) mentions that beef, pork and sheep/goat were important sources of food but gives no details beyond quantification.

Boranga's (1997) analysis of faunal remains from the camps of the VOC *Zeewijk* survivors was the only available comparative study for identifying seventeenth-century Dutch subsistence and butchery behaviours. The *Zeewijk* was a similar vessel to the *Batavia*, carrying approximately 208 people from the Netherlands to Java. The *Zeewijk* left the Netherlands in 1726 and wrecked in the Pelsaert Group of the Abrolhos Islands (Ingelman-Sundberg 1977). The *Zeewijk* survivors retrieved four barrels and 17 cases of meat (pork and beef) from the wreck, which they combined with fish and sea lion meat to survive for eight months (Graeff 1726).

The analysis of butchery bones from the *Zeewijk* survivors' camps, although not well documented, suggests a pattern of butchery similar to bones from the *Batavia* assemblages. Unfortunately, the details on butchery patterns in the *Zeewijk* assemblages do not contain enough information (such as type of butchery, orientation, size and frequency) to allow a comprehensive comparison to the *Batavia* assemblages. In the *Zeewijk* assemblages, butchered cow and pig ribs and vertebrae are the most frequently represented butchered elements for introduced mammals (Boranga 1997:78-82). This is a similar pattern to pork and beef remains found in the *Batavia* assemblages. Boranga's butchery patterns are also similar to Piper's (1991) findings for nineteenth-century foodways for St. Helena Island in Queensland, as mentioned above.

The resemblance of the *Batavia* survivors' faunal remains to a nineteenth-century Australian butchery pattern and a seventeenth-century Dutch butchery pattern is a result of Boranga's methodology. Boranga aimed to use faunal remains from Gun Island to identify socio-economic differences in the eleven areas excavated. Without comparative seventeenth-century Dutch butchery data, Boranga (1997:71) used butchery units identified by Schultz and Gust's (1983) as indicators of socio-economic status. However, the use of butchery units from nineteenth-century American urban contexts is arguably inappropriate for identifying butchery patterns in barrelled meat from the seventeenth-century Netherlands. By identifying butchery units in terms of Schultz and Gust's model, Boranga forced a nineteenth century butchery pattern onto an assemblage from a different time and context, where the nineteenth century pattern may not have existed. Whilst it is possible that butchery patterns observed in nineteenth century-urban American deposits are similar to butchery patterns observed in seventeenth-century Dutch barrelled meat, this has not yet been demonstrated.

Potential sources of information on sea voyage and shipwreck victuals are excavations of VOC shipwrecks. The VOC *Vergulde Draeck* wrecked in 1656 at Ledge Point (Western Australia), and excavations on the wreck in the 1970s recovered 663 cow and pig bones (Green 1977). Ribs, vertebrae, scapulae and 'leg' (humeri) are mentioned by Green (1977:244-247), but no details on quantification or butchery patterns are provided (except for an illustration of a longitudinally sawn vertebrae). Stanbury (1975:47) notes 34 pieces of mammal bone recovered from the *Batavia* wreck, but offers no comparative data relevant to this thesis.

Native Mammals, Fish and Birds

Both halves of a tammar's sawn left femur were found in the Beacon Island assemblage. The femur was not related to the *Batavia* survivors subsistence behaviours because the bones were still green, and therefore deposited too recently to be contemporary with the *Batavia* survivors. One caudal vertebra of a tammar showed sawing down one side. The ventral portions of four sawn sea lion ribs were present in the Beacon Island assemblage. One sea lion right humerus had some saw marks near the proximal end. There were no butchered unknown native mammal bones in the Beacon Island assemblage, and no butchered native mammal bones at all in the West Wallabi Island assemblage.

Four Sparidae vertebrae and 15 unidentified fish vertebrae in the Beacon Island assemblage had been sawn laterally. No fish bones in the West Wallabi Island assemblage showed any signs of butchering. No bird bones in either assemblage had been butchered.

Burnt Bone

Introduced Mammals

Two introduced mammal bones displayed signs of burning in the West Wallabi assemblage (table 5.12). One bone was a sheep/goat rib shaft that had been butchered to divide the carcass into more than two units. The other bone was an unidentified fragment. No introduced mammal bones in the Beacon Island assemblage were burnt.

	Beacon				West Wallabi			
	NISP		Mass		NISP		Mass	
	N	%	g	%	N	%	g	%
Introduced mammals	0	0	0	0	2	0.6	10.03	2.53
Native mammals	1	0.03	0.96	0.01	30	8.98	25.25	6.38
Fish	1	0.03	0.08	0.001	1	0.3	0.08	0.02
Birds	0	0	0	0	6	1.8	3.94	0.99
Unknown mammals	0	0	0	0	21	6.29	12.05	3.04
Unknowns	27	0.79	3.12	0.035	12	3.59	1.42	0.36

Table 5.12
Numbers of burnt bone specimens by each class in the Beacon and West Wallabi Island assemblages

Native Mammals

A total of 30 native mammal specimens in the West Wallabi Island assemblage showed signs of burning. Tammar bones accounted for 21 of these, with six vertebrae, three mandibles, two calcanei and a variety of long bone fragments. Nine burnt native mammal specimens were unidentified in the West Wallabi Island assemblage, and one specimen in the Beacon Island assemblage.

Fish and Birds

One fish specimen in each assemblage showed signs of burning; a Sparidae beak fragment in the West Wallabi Island assemblage and an unidentified fragment in the Beacon Island assemblage. Three burnt bird humerus fragments were found in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. One specimen represents an Accipitridiform, one a Shearwater and one is an unidentified specimen. Three unidentified burnt bird bone fragments were also identified in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. There was one unidentified burnt bird bone identified in the Beacon Island assemblage.

Unknown

A total of 27 non-mammal unidentified burnt bones were found in the Beacon Island assemblage and 12 in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. A further 21 unidentified mammal bones showed signs of burning in the West Wallabi Island assemblage.

Burnt bones (none of which show signs of butchery) make up 0.84% (NISP) and 0.05% (mass) of the Beacon Island assemblage and 21.55% (NISP) and 13.32% (mass) of the West Wallabi Island assemblage. There is a clear difference in the proportions of

burnt bone in each assemblage, which potentially indicates distinct differences in the subsistence behaviours of each group of survivors. If the Beacon Island assemblage had the higher proportion of burnt bone it could be explained as the result of post-*Batavia* occupation rather than related to the *Batavia* survivors. The West Wallabi Island excavations recovered only seventeenth-century Dutch artefacts in context with the faunal remains, so the burnt bones can be attributed to the *Batavia* survivors.

Although the differences in the survivors' subsistence behaviours regarding burnt bone appear real, the usefulness of these observations is compromised because it is unlikely the two areas are comparable in terms of subsistence activity areas. The area from where the Beacon Island assemblage was recovered cannot be definitely associated with a specific habitation site or structure related to the *Batavia* survivors. The excavation data for this area is 'lost or in a confused state' (Bevacqua 1974d:7; in 1999 the Maritime Museum was unable to locate any of it, Stanbury pers comm 1999), although Green and Stanbury (1988:5) provide some details and interpretations of the excavations. Green and Stanbury say that artefacts recovered from this area include 'a bone comb, button, porcelain and majolica sherds, metal fragments and so on' (1988:5). They also report that

a large quantity of midden material was recovered from the Site "C" surface area among which were butchered animal bones, a musket ball and a copper alloy fish-hook (Green and Stanbury 1988:5).

Assuming that the survivors kept living and waste areas separate, this area on Beacon Island is probably a site where faunal remains were disposed of after consumption.

The faunal remains from West Wallabi Island were excavated from in and around the Slaughter Point stone structure, a site containing Dutch artefacts associated with *Batavia* survivors (Bevacqua 1974c; O'Loughlin 1964; 1966). Aquinas College reported finding burnt bones in two subsurface fire pits at the Slaughter Point structure (O'Loughlin 1966:12; Bevacqua 1974c:5). The burnt bones were described as 'mainly those of the tammar', with some sea lion and Shearwater bones (O'Loughlin 1966:12). The previous finds of burnt bone and hearths at the structure associated with the West Wallabi Island assemblage indicates that the assemblage came from a preparation and consumption site. At this site, fauna was cooked and consumed, with waste being disposed of in the hearths and dumped elsewhere. It is more likely that the bones were burnt during disposal rather than cooking because the bones were burnt completely.

No burnt bones were recovered in the 1967 Beacon Island excavations and the excavations did not include any hearths.

Completeness Analysis

Introduced Mammals

In the Beacon Island assemblage introduced mammal bones are highly fragmented, with 45% (NISP) represented by a quarter or less of an element (figure 5.4, table 5.13). Pig bones are evenly represented in terms of degree of completeness, but 47% (NISP) of sheep/goat bones 47% (NISP) of cow bones are represented by a quarter or less of an element. In the West Wallabi Island assemblage there were only five introduced mammal bones, so it is not possible describe the assemblage as intact or highly fragmented. In the Beacon Island assemblage 4.95% (NISP) of introduced mammal bones were excluded from the completeness analysis because the level of completeness could not be deduced (for example, where an element represented by a fragment was not known a measurement of its completeness could not be made). One bone specimen (20% NISP) of introduced mammal in the West Wallabi Island assemblage could not be assigned a completeness value.

Figure 5.4
Trends in degrees of fragmentation for pig, sheep/goat and cow bones from the Beacon Island assemblage

	NISP			
	frg 1/4	frg 2/4	frg 3/4	whl
pig	9	4	6	7
sheep/goat	40	12	10	20
cow	16	12	4	0

Table 5.13
Table of NISP by degrees of fragmentation of pig, sheep/ goat from the Beacon Island assemblage

Native Mammals

Native mammal bone from both assemblages tended to be less fragmented than introduced mammal bone as shown in figure 5.5 and table 5.14. Tammar and sea lion bone from the Beacon Island assemblage are represented more by whole bones (53% NISP for tammar and 60% NISP for sea lion) than any other degree of fragmentation. In the West Wallabi Island assemblage there is a similar pattern of tammar bone representation, with 40% (NISP) of bones whole and 28.7% represented by three-quarters or more of an element. In the Beacon Island assemblage 13.8% (NISP) of native mammal bones could not be assigned a completeness value, and 14.5% (NISP) could not be given values in the West Wallabi Island assemblage.

Figure 5.5
Trends in degrees of fragmentation for tammar and sea lion bone from the Beacon and West Wallabi Island assemblages

	Beacon					West Wallabi								
	NISP					NISP								
	frg	1/4	frg	2/4	frg	3/4	whl	frg	1/4	frg	2/4	frg	3/4	whl
tammar		19		10		32	71		21		4		23	32
sea lion		13		6		15	51		0		0		0	0

Table 5.14

Table of NISP by degrees of fragmentation of tammar and seal lion bone from the Beacon and West Wallabi Island assemblages

There are at least two possible explanations for the differences in levels of fragmentation between native and introduced mammals. The introduced mammal bones tend to be more fragmented possibly because they were more intensively worked for marrow extraction. The survivors may have ground up introduced mammal bones to extract marrow and make soups. Another explanation for highly fragmented introduced mammal bones is that the bones arrived on the islands in a more fragmented form because they were butchered and barrelled. The survivors probably made no attempt to make native mammals transportable or barrel them, so native mammal bones were probably fragmented only enough to extract meat. Marrow may not have been extracted from native mammals to the same extent as introduced mammals because the survivors might not have been familiar with native mammals, and tammar bones are a less efficient (in terms of energy expenditure and return) source of marrow than large introduced mammal bones.

Fish, Bird and Unidentified

Fish bones generally show a similar trend in fragmentation to introduced mammals, with a relatively high number of whole bones (figure 5.6, table 5.15). For fish and bird bones, this trend favours the representation of whole bones, and is assumed to reflect taphonomic processes rather than resource extraction. The amount of marrow or other non-meat resources available from fish and bird bones is negligible. It important to note that 51.8% (NISP) of fish bones from the Beacon Island assemblage and 52.6 % (NISP) from the West Wallabi Island assemblage were not included in the completeness analysis because it was not possible to know how complete they were. The excluded bones may represent highly fragmented specimens that might substantially change the trend in fragmentation if they were included in the analysis. Consequently, it is not appropriate to view the trend in fragmentation as representative of all fish bones in the two assemblages.

Figure 5.6

Trends in degrees of fragmentation for fish and bird bone from the Beacon and West Wallabi Island assemblages

	Beacon				West Wallabi			
	NISP				NISP			
	frg 1/4	frg 2/4	frg 3/4	whl	frg 1/4	frg 2/4	frg 3/4	whl
fish	127	106	384	496	2	2	3	2
bird	29	17	87	252	9	0	48	51

Table 5.15

Table of NISP by degrees of fragmentation of fish and bird bone from the Beacon and West Wallabi Island assemblages

Figure 5.6 shows that bird bones are highly represented by whole bones. Whole bird bones account for 55.7% (NISP) of bird bones from the Beacon Island assemblage and 31.8% (NISP) of bird bones from the West Wallabi Island assemblage. It is assumed that bird bone, like fish bone, was not extensively worked beyond meat extraction. In the case of the small birds found commonly on the Wallabi Group, meat extraction does not necessarily involve bone breakage. The high proportion of whole bird bones in the assemblages suggests that site formation processes such as the burrowing of shearwaters and trampling had only a slight effect on the completeness of bird bone (and bone of other taxa) in the assemblages. It was not possible to classify unidentified bone (of any class) to a completeness level.

Fracture analysis

Two fracture types were identified in the Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island assemblages; spiral fracturing and stepped fracturing, which appear only on tammar and bird bones in each assemblage (table 5.16).

	Beacon		West Wallabi	
	stepped	spiral	stepped	spiral
tammar	8	9	0	2
bird	35	14	0	0

Table 5.16

Table of NISP by fracture type of tammar and bird bone from the Beacon Island and West Wallabi Island assemblages

Sea lion, introduced mammal and fish bones were either butchered (sawn or sheared) rather than fractured, or fractured in ways that were not identified in the system employed here. It has been argued that spiral bone fractures can be indicative of human modification (Dart 1957), but more recent work has shown that any number of taphonomic processes can cause spiral fractures, including trampling (Haynes 1983; Myers, Voorhies and Corner 1980) and carnivore gnawing (Binford 1981). Lyman (1994a:324; 1987b) argues that the agent of fracture cannot be deduced exclusively from the fracture, but requires the analysis of multiple attributes.

It is possible the survivors fractured tammar bones to extract marrow or to use as tools. None of the fractured tammar bones were burnt or butchered in the Beacon Island assemblage. One fractured bone was burnt in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. The weak correlation of fracturing to other signs of cultural modification (butchering and burning) suggest that bone fracturing was probably not a significant subsistence behaviour for the *Batavia* survivors. The absence of fractured sea lion bones in the assemblages is interesting, as sea lion bones contain more grease and marrow than tammar bones. If the survivors were in stressful conditions of limited subsistence resources they might be expected to extract marrow to maximise the resources that the available mammals can provide. Perhaps sea lion bones were broken to extract marrow and then disposed in an unexcavated area, away from the habitation site to keep the living space relatively clear and hygienic. The fracturing of bird bone does not seem related to marrow extraction because bird bones contain very little in-bone nutrients, compared to tammars, sea lions and introduced mammals. It is assumed that the bird

bone fracturing is the result of antemortem processes (living animals breaking their bones), scavengers feeding on the bones and post-depositional processes (trampling, crushing and other taphonomic processes).

Summary

This chapter has presented data that suggests a difference in subsistence behaviours between the two groups of survivors. Proportions of native mammal are higher in the West Wallabi Island assemblage, while proportions of salvaged mammals are higher in the Beacon Island assemblage. There are higher proportions of fish, but lower proportions of bird in the Beacon Island assemblage than in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. Burnt bone was found in high proportions in the West Wallabi Island assemblage compared to the Beacon Island assemblage, suggesting a difference in food preparation or in activity areas are represented by the assemblages. Salvaged mammal bones from bone assemblages are more fragmented than native fauna bones, possibly because salvaged mammal bones were already fragmented for packing into barrels. Data on butchery showed a pattern in salvaged fauna bones consistent with barrelled meat. Fracturing analysis suggests the survivors did not extensively extract marrow or make bone tools.

Chapter Six Discussion and Conclusion

Discussion of Results

This thesis has presented an analysis of archaeological and historical data relating to the subsistence behaviours of the *Batavia* survivors. The results of this analysis can be used to address the predictions introduced in chapter one.

1. *The group on Beacon Island subsisted mainly on salvaged fauna, while those on West Wallabi Island subsisted mainly on native fauna.*

The results of the faunal analysis showed a high proportion of native fauna in the West Wallabi Island assemblage contrasted against a high proportion of salvaged fauna in the Beacon Island assemblage. Considering taphonomic and site formation processes, the observed proportions can be considered representative of resources utilised by the *Batavia* survivors. The disparity between the two sample sizes was minimised by comparing proportions of taxa. Consequently, proximity and access to the wreck seem to have been important variables in determining available resources. The survivors on Beacon Island were close to the wreck and historic sources suggest that barrels of food floated onto the island. Historic sources do not specifically mention barrels of meat, but the abundance of salvaged fauna in the archaeological record suggests salvaged fauna was an important resource. The absence of written discussion of salvaged meat may have resulted from those writing the records not consuming salvaged meat. Possible reasons why salvaged meat was not consumed include being distant from the wreck, such as the survivors on West Wallabi Island and the hoarding of barrelled meat by the mutineers.

However, the resolution of the archaeological record was not sufficient to infer hoarding or sharing through butchery. That said, it was possible to discern that butchered ribs and vertebrae in the assemblages are consistent with butchery patterns of barrelled bones. The pattern of species diversity and abundance on Beacon Island offers an alternative approach to the issue of hoarding. While the proportion of

salvaged fauna is high on Beacon Island, the proportion of fish bones is also high. The high representation of fish bones suggests that salvaged fauna was not sufficiently abundant to feed everyone on the island, and fish was caught to supplement the diet. The mutineers' hoarding, as described in the historic sources, may have forced people on Beacon Island to eat fish to survive. Sea lion and birds, found in the archaeological assemblage and mentioned in the historic sources, also appear to have supplemented the diet for survivors on Beacon Island. The abundance of salvaged fauna and fish suggests a bimodal distribution of resource classes potentially confirming the scenario of mutineers hoarding salvaged fauna and survivors deprived of salvaged fauna forced to subsist on native fauna.

Alternatively, the abundance of fish remains on Beacon Island may reflect a change from salvaged fauna to native fauna. As supplies of salvaged fauna depleted, fish may have become the main subsistence resource. The poor stratigraphic resolution in the archaeological excavations did not measure temporal change, and the historic sources do not describe a change from salvaged to native fauna. At this stage, there is insufficient data to confirm change over time in resources on Beacon Island. The explanation of the bimodal distribution of fish and salvaged fauna could potentially be explained by hoarding and change over time: salvaged resources may have been hoarded initially, and then the focus may have changed to fish as salvaged fauna became depleted, which the mutineers may have continued to hoard.

For the survivors on West Wallabi Island, native fauna appears to have been the sole subsistence resource. Tammars in the West Wallabi Island assemblage have the highest %NISP and %mass values for any identified bone from both islands. In part, this might result from their natural abundance, or perhaps the large number shot by Stokes and Dakin in later activities. It seems likely that the tamarin bones were associated with the *Batavia* survivors because they were burnt and possibly found in association with hearths in a *Batavia* period structure. The proportion of fish in the West Wallabi Island assemblage was not as high as in the Beacon Island assemblage, suggesting that fish was not heavily depended on, or was not recovered in the excavations. The proportion of bird bones was high in the West Wallabi Island assemblage, but this may be influenced by the natural abundance of birds on West Wallabi. The uniformly high proportion of native fauna suggests the survivors on West Wallabi Island probably shared a diet of tammars, bird and some fish. Changes over time, although undetectable in this context, may have required expending more energy

to obtain the same resources. As resources in the area near the stone shelter became depleted, and the prey more wary of the hunters, the survivors on West Wallabi Island may have had to expand their catchment area and change their strategies. The low proportions of fish in the West Wallabi assemblage might reflect the absence of fishing equipment, the absence of a need for fish, or the context of the group.

In addition, the social context of each group may have influenced what resources were exploited. On West Wallabi Island the survivors were mainly soldiers intended to serve at the Dutch colonies in Indonesia. Soldiers may have been most familiar with terrestrial resources because their activities were generally land-based. The soldiers on West Wallabi Island may have consumed tamar and birds because they were not familiar or comfortable with marine resources such as fish. The low proportion of fish in the West Wallabi Island assemblage could result from a reluctance or inability of the soldiers to catch fish. Conversely, the survivors on Beacon Island included a majority of sailors and experienced sea travellers who were probably experienced with fishing and utilising marine resources. In this case, the subsistence experience of each group may have influenced the subsistence resources consumed by the survivors.

- 2. Patterns of food preparation were different for each group. The variables of resource scarcity and food-sharing behaviour influence patterns of food preparation.*

Evidence for differences in food preparation can be found in the proportions of burnt bone in each assemblage. The assemblage from West Wallabi Island has a higher proportion of burnt bone in all classes of fauna than the Beacon Island assemblage. The difference in proportions of burnt bone may be because the survivors on West Wallabi used fires more than the survivors on Beacon Island. Bone tends to be burnt during disposal, rather than cooking, so the different proportions may reflect the recovery of material from different types of activity areas. The areas excavated on Beacon Island did not include hearths, while two hearths were found in the West Wallabi Island excavations. The absence of hearths on Beacon Island could suggest food was not cooked, except that historic sources describe several cooking events on Beacon Island. The difference in proportions of burnt bone possibly reflects the contexts of the areas excavated. The West Wallabi Island assemblage was excavated from a context of hearths inside a stone structure, while the Beacon Island assemblage was excavated

from a context without hearths in an open area. Further excavations on Beacon Island may reveal *Batavia* survivors' hearths, provided they are intact.

Butchered bone occurs most frequently in the Beacon Island assemblage, presumably representative of salvaged fauna. The butchery patterns are consistent with barrelled meat and are not necessarily reflections of the survivors' butchering practises. Trends in fragmentation suggest salvaged fauna on Beacon Island (the West Wallabi Island sample of salvaged mammal was too small to make confident inferences) was highly fragmented while native fauna from both assemblages favoured the representation of complete bones. This pattern, if representative of the survivors' behaviours, suggests a similar usage of native fauna on both islands. Neither group of survivors appear to have extensively fragmented native fauna bones for extraction of marrow or to make tools (such as fishing hooks). The trends in fragmentation may reflect that fauna salvaged from the *Batavia* arrived already fragmented. Analysis of fracturing patterns did not suggest a significant pattern of survivors breaking bones, but instead appeared to be a result of Post-*Batavia* taphonomic and site formation processes.

Evaluating differences in food preparation was made difficult by the small sample sizes for butchered and burnt bone and the problem of comparing two assemblages that potentially represent several different activity areas. Therefore, it is not possible to confidently state that the survivors prepared their food differently as a result of scarcity of resources or differences in sharing.

3. *The degree of resource sharing within each island's population reflects resource abundance, social organisation and the relationship between the two groups.*

It has not been possible to make confident inferences on the sharing of resources within each group using the archaeological record. Historic sources suggest hoarding by the mutineers on Beacon Island and sharing by the soldiers and other survivors on West Wallabi Island. The perspective of the predicant and the *Leyden Ferry-boat* authors of the mutiny may have biased these historic sources towards the favourable representation of the loyalist soldiers on West Wallabi Island, while describing the mutineers as maliciously hoarding food on Beacon Island.

Historic sources suggest that the soldiers on West Wallabi Island were organised in a military-style chain of command. Given that the loyalist soldiers were threatened by violent mutineers, defence was an important concern for the soldiers. This is reflected in the strategic location of their stone shelters close to freshwater sinkholes and archaeological finds of weapons made from barrel hoops and nails (Bevacqua 1974c:17). There might have been a division of labour to build fortifications and shelter, keep a defensive lookout for the mutineers and search for food. Food sharing would be a necessity if there was a division of labour, with part of the population focussed on defence, another part would have provided food for the entire group. Food gathering may have had to become more efficient as the population on West Wallabi Island increased. O'Loughlin (1965:35) has suggested that the stone structure at Slaughter Point was expanded to provide shelter for the people fleeing the mutineers to West Wallabi Island.

The soldiers were presumably more experienced with crisis situations involving shortages of food and supplies and threats of attack. They probably were able to survive efficiently given the abundant fauna on West Wallabi Island. The record of the predicant and the *Leyden Ferry-boat* authors indicate that the soldiers assisted everyone on West Wallabi Island with food and incorporated them into defensive activities. The group on Beacon Island appear less unified, with the mutineers hoarding food and others starving to death. The predicant writes that the mutineers' tents were grouped away from the rest of the survivors, and that they would invite people to dine with them (Bastiaensz in Drake-Brockman 1963:265). The mutineers were also documented salvaging treasure from the wreck, so it is possible they were able to collect and hoard stores of salvaged meat. Gibbs (1992) describes a find of sea lion bones under coral slabs on Beacon Island and proposes that survivors may have cached meat. The mutineers may have prevented other survivors from receiving any food and the sea lion cache might represent an attempt by survivors to secretly store food.

In summary, the archaeological record of the *Batavia* survivors analysed in this thesis did not provide detailed information on social organisation. However, the historical record suggests the soldiers were organised according to a military-style system that involved everyone on West Wallabi Island and sharing of food. In contrast, the survivors on Beacon Island were divided into two groups; the mutineers, who hoarded food amongst themselves, and the other survivors, who, in the crisis of

mutiny, were unable to organise themselves and presumably survived by individual foraging and fishing.

Although evidence of inter-site sharing is limited using the archaeological record, intra-site sharing appears evident. Tammars bones were found in the Beacon Island assemblage and salvaged mammal bones were found in the West Wallabi assemblage. The most parsimonious explanation for these distributions (in the context of the *Batavia* survivors) is that when Pelsaert returned, native and salvaged fauna was distributed throughout the islands to people who were still alive. Pelsaert may have taken tammars from West and East Wallabi Islands to the survivors on Beacon Island. Pelsaert may have given supplies of salvaged fauna to survivors on West Wallabi Island because resources may have become scarce on West Wallabi Island. However, this archaeological evidence may also result from inter-island access of resources not detailed in the historic record. Alternatively, the tammars on Beacon Island and introduced mammal on West Wallabi Island possibly resulted from later occupation of the islands, unrelated to the *Batavia* survivors.

The degree of resource sharing, as inferred from the archaeological and historic records, appears to have been influenced by the social context and organisation of each group. The abundance of resources may have influenced resource sharing but it was not possible to demonstrate this using the archaeological or historic records. The lack of stratigraphic control on the archaeological record precludes any confident conclusions about sharing resources between the two groups prior to Pelsaert's return. However, historic sources suggest that the contact between the soldiers and the mutineers was hostile, and that transfer of resources did not take place.

Discussion of subsistence resources in survival contexts

Gibbs (n.d.:6) has suggested that subsistence resources for shipwreck survivors would initially be derived from the ship through direct salvage or collection of flotsam and jetsam. Survivors would probably also investigate the surrounding environment and assess available resources for the implementation of a foraging strategy (Gibbs n.d.:6). In the context of the *Batavia* survivors, there are three variables that influence the organisation of the survivors' subsistence resources:

1) *The availability of resources from the ship.*

Food and water were stored in the hold of the *Batavia*, which sustained damage during the wreck event, destroying some of these resources. Proximity and access to the wreck influenced the relative importance of salvaged resources for the two groups of *Batavia* survivors. The mutineers and others on Beacon Island, subsisting on a combination of salvaged and native fauna, were close to the wreck and controlled access with a small boat. The survivors on West Wallabi Island were distant and isolated from the wreck and presumably subsisted entirely on native fauna.

2) *The nature of the local environment, and the ability of the survivors to utilise native resources.*

For the *Batavia* survivors, differences in the local environment were significant factors in organising subsistence resources. Archaeological analysis showed that the survivors on West Wallabi Island, who had access to abundant native fauna, subsisted almost entirely on native resources. In contrast, the survivors on Beacon Island relied on salvaged fauna and fish, presumably because of the absence of abundant native terrestrial fauna. Analysis of the historic records suggests the *Batavia* survivors adapted to native resources rapidly and the survivors' adaptation was influenced by social conditions. It could be speculated that the mutineers controlled resources on Beacon Island and potentially deprived survivors from exploiting native resources Beacon Island. It is interesting that fish were not highly represented in the West Wallabi Island assemblage. It was not possible to determine if this was a result of an absence of adequate fishing equipment, the survivors' preference for terrestrial fauna or a problem in archaeological sampling.

3) *The social context and organisation of the shipwreck survivors.*

The organisation of the survivors after the shipwreck influences the provision and management of resources (Gibbs n.d.:6). Historic sources suggest the mutineers organised themselves into an exclusive oligarchy and hoarded salvaged resources. The survivors on West Wallabi Island appear to have had a more open organisation, perhaps based on a military structure, where everyone was involved in maintaining the camp and resources were shared. In the case of the *Batavia*, two different social contexts developed, each with contrasting systems of resource management and distribution.

Other issues

There are other issues relevant to the *Batavia* survivors that did not become apparent in the analysis of archaeological and historic sources. In his archaeological study of adaptation, Kirch (1980) writes that while the environment acts as a limiting factor, adaptation can be influenced by information brought into, and acquired from, a situation by adapting individuals. Minc (1986) demonstrates that hunter-gatherer societies use secular and sacred oral traditions to incorporate important subsistence information for surviving times of stress and crisis. The *Batavia* survivors may have mediated their crises with previous knowledge of successful behaviours in shipwreck conditions. For example, stories of shipwrecks were popular in seventeenth-century Europe (the story of the *Batavia* was to run for several editions in Dutch and French), and sailors and passengers aboard the *Batavia* may have been aware of potential shipwreck survival strategies from exposure to stories. People aboard the *Batavia* may have been familiar with at least one of the forty-five other VOC mutinies of the seventeenth century (Bruijn and van Heslinga 1982). Such knowledge of shipwreck and mutiny situations was potentially an adaptive advantage because it may have led to behaviours that maximised survival.

The shipwreck and insurrection of the *Batavia* survivors can be described as a 'revolutionary' environmental change (Thoday 1953:110), where individuals colonise a radically different environment. According to Thoday (1953), this type of change pressures adaptive change stronger than 'cyclic' or 'unidirectional and continued change' and results in the greatest range of behavioural variability. Thoday's descriptions agree with Shnirelman's (1992) argument that crisis was one of the most important stimuli for changes in subsistence behaviours for hunter-gatherer societies. The *Batavia* survivors' crises appear to have caused a high range of behavioural variability in their exploitation of diverse resources. However, it is significant the different social contexts of the survivors, as well as the different environments, limited potential subsistence resources.

In complex societies, archaeologists have demonstrated how social relations can be defined and maintained through food (Gumerman 1997). For example, the *Batavia* mutineers hoarded the best food—symbolic of the power they held—while others on Beacon Island were excluded from the mutineers' subsistence system. Faunal analysis has been used to study socioeconomic status, ethnicity, gender and other aspects of culture (Crabtree 1990; Schulz and Gust 1983; Rothschild and Balkwill 1993; Lyman

1987a). In this thesis there were insufficient details on recovery methods and comparative archaeological studies to investigate socioeconomic status, ethnicity or gender. However, with the aid of historic sources, it was possible to assess the impact of two contrasting types of social organisation on subsistence behaviours.

Implications

The implications of this study are that the processes of adaptation of the *Batavia* survivors to the crises of shipwreck and insurrection were complex, particularistic and structured by social and environmental contexts. For investigating shipwreck survivors in general the results of this study imply that the historical context of the voyage and shipwreck is equally important as the environmental contexts of the wreck and survivors' camps when researching the survivors' behaviours.

More universally, the implications of this study are that environmental and ecological processes are not sufficient explanatory devices for investigating past human behaviour. Historical contexts, particularly in the case of short-term, small-scale events, are essential for providing underlying causal processes (Wylie 1982:204). Without historical context, the differences in the *Batavia* faunal assemblages would probably be ascribed to environmental variables alone, thus neglecting the influence of social context.

In this thesis it is proposed that the role of history and of individuals be asserted in archaeological explanation. History, as defined by Collingwood (1946), is the perception of human behaviour as situation specific action, rather than as a behavioural or normative response (Hodder 1986:97). The role of the individual in archaeological explanation is, amongst other things, as an ideologically informed agent of cultural variability (Gargett 1992:128). Archaeology is a historical science because it frequently creates explanations that are narratives where antecedent events are connected in causal ways to change (Gargett 1992:119; Flannery 1986:514). Keat and Urry write that:

Answers to why-questions (that is, requests for causal explanations) require answers to how- and what-questions. Thus, if asked *why* something occurs, we must show how some event or change brings about a new state of affairs, by describing the way in which the structures and mechanisms that are present respond to the initial change. (1975:31)

Archaeological explanations incorporating historical context can provide narratives that incorporate cause and effect relationships. This thesis does not recommend the abandonment of the study of process (which is frequently just long-term patterns of behaviour by multiple agents), but a demonstration that it is possible to combine process, historical context and individual agency in archaeological explanation (Flannery 1999). Explaining the subsistence behaviours of the *Batavia* survivors has incorporated processes of adaptation, the general context of seventeenth-century European culture and the small-scale contexts of mutineers and soldiers, and the roles of individuals such as Cornelisz, the leader of the mutineers.

Future Research

To improve our understanding of the *Batavia* survivors' behaviours, a comprehensive synthesis of previous archaeological and historical research is recommended. A suitable long-term research design, as outlined by Gibbs (1992:18-26), should be implemented. The research design should include all of the land sites associated with the *Batavia* survivors. Further excavations are recommended only in the context of a long-term research project. Pelsaert's salvage operations may have removed Dutch artefactual material but discarded animal bones were probably ignored during the salvage process and by later seekers of relics (Gibbs 1992:5). The selective removal of material by Pelsaert and later visitors suggests that faunal material from the *Batavia* survivors might be recovered from previously excavated areas (Gibbs 1992:22). A full analysis of already recovered artefacts may provide further information on the behaviour and social organisation of the survivors.

Future studies of the *Batavia* and other shipwreck situations might benefit from the application of catastrophe theory and the analysis of organisational structure and scalar stress. Catastrophe theory was defined by Renfrew (1978) as an attempt describe discontinuous change in behaviour in terms of smooth changes in the underlying causative factors. Trigger writes that:

Catastrophe theory treats the question of how, as the result of particular conjunctions of internal states, a set of fluctuating variables can produce discontinuous effects (1989:321).

Catastrophe theory has been applied to long-term, large-scale processes such as the origins of agriculture and state formation, and may be useful for explaining short-term, small-scale events such as shipwrecks. For example, interactions between Pelsaert, the mutineers, the soldiers, and other passengers aboard the *Batavia* represent 'conjunctions of internal states'. Some of the resulting 'fluctuating variables' may be defined as sharing or hoarding resources, and killing people or including them in the group.

Analysis of organisational structure and scalar stress may be another potentially useful approach to survival studies. In many shipwreck incidents, the shipboard authority structure reproduces itself in the group of survivors (Gibbs n.d.:3-5). The organisational structure of the survivors, as observed with the *Batavia* survivors, can influence survival success. For the *Batavia*, shipboard structure was replicated with a radical alteration of the basis of its legitimisation. Aspects influencing organisational structure included: group size, the number of decision-makers and the nature of organisation (hierarchically or horizontally organised). Scalar stress occurs when information-processing performance declines, resulting in decision errors, decreased consensus and member satisfaction, and reduced survival success (Johnson 1982; cf. Kirch 1980). Investigating sources of scalar stress and differences in organisational structure between pre- and post-shipwreck contexts and between different groups of survivors may be useful in understanding survival situations.

Further research into the subsistence behaviours of the *Batavia* survivors and other shipwreck survivors should be focussed on the contexts in which food is procured, consumed and disposed, faunal remains, human skeletal analysis and coprolite analysis. Bone chemistry analysis can be used in the research of subsistence behaviours (Pate 1994). Elements such as aluminium, barium, calcium, iron, potassium and strontium in bones have been used as dietary indicators, although Ezzo (1994) suggests that only barium and strontium can be considered valid dietary indicators. Ratios of Strontium can indicate if a diet was mainly carnivorous or vegetarian (Schoneninger 1979). A particularly useful technique for investigating the contribution of salvaged and native resources is the analysis of ratios of carbon and nitrogen isotopes in human bones. The ratios of carbon and nitrogen isotopes, ^{15}N , ^{13}C and ^{12}C , differs between marine and terrestrial sources of protein. The analysis of the isotope ratios in human bones can show whether diet was based on land or marine resources

(Price 1989; Chisholm, Nelson and Schwarcz 1982; Schoneninger, Deniro and Tauber 1983).

One of the limitations of isotope analysis is that it is only relevant for observing long-term dietary behaviours, and probably unable to provide the resolution required for investigating short-term events such as a shipwreck survival situation. Analysis of human tooth wear is an appropriate technique for the analysis of short-term events. Tooth abrasion patterns can indicate processes of cooking and whether the diet was meat or vegetable based (Puech 1979).

Future excavations should also focus on midden and refuse areas for the potential to recover desiccated or mineralised feces, known as coprolites. Although the conditions the Abrolhos Islands may not favour the preservation of coprolites, they are useful for reconstructing diets. Components of coprolites can include: bacteria, fungus, pollen, phytoliths, parasites, seeds leaves and other plant remains, vertebrate remains, insects, and mineral and chemical components (Reinhard and Bryant 1992). Analysis of the *Batavia* survivors' coprolites might reveal the health of the survivors and whether flora was consumed.

Conclusion

This thesis concludes that the subsistence behaviours of the *Batavia* survivors included native and salvaged fauna, and were dependant upon the social context of the survivors and availability of the resources. The implications are that archaeological explanation can benefit from the integration of historical context and consideration of the role of individuals. Future research is advocated in the form of a long-term program, with potential theoretical approaches including catastrophe theory and organisational structure analysis, and potential technical approaches including artefact analysis, bone analysis and the analysis of coprolites.

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Appendix A

Glossary

Anterior	A directional term for bones meaning towards the front or the head or body (Landon 1996:128).
Assemblage	The entire collection of material from an archaeological site.
Distal	A directional term denoting the end of limb bones that are further away from the body (Landon 1996:128).
Element	A specific bone or skeletal part in an animal.
Lateral	A directional term meaning away from the mid-line of the body.
MNI	The minimum number of individuals.
NISP	The number of identified specimens.
%MNI	The minimum number of individuals by percentage.
%NISP	The number of identified specimens by percentage.
Post-cranial	All the parts of the skeleton that are below or behind the head (Landon 1996:128).
Proximal	A directional term denoting the end of limb bones that are closest to the body (Landon 1996:128).
Specimen	Any piece of bone.
Taxa	The plural of taxon.
Taxon	A particular taxonomic group of organisms into hierarchical categories that reflect their relationships. Categories include, among others, class, order, family, genus and species (Landon 1996:128).

Appendix B

The chi-square test is a common technique for ascertaining if the data in a contingency table provides significant evidence of an association between the two variables (Fletcher and Lock 1991:116). The use of the chi-square test assumes that the data is ^{non-}parametric, or has a distribution ^{that departs from} similar to a normal curve, which may not always be the case. The test compares observed frequencies with those expected under the null hypothesis of no association (Fletcher and Lock 1991:116). The test is described as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E} \quad \text{Where} \quad \begin{array}{l} O = \text{observed frequencies} \\ E = \text{expected frequencies} \end{array}$$

The expected frequency is calculated by: $E = \frac{(\text{row total})(\text{column total})}{\text{grand total}}$

In this case:

	Beacon	West Wallabi
richness	22	13
sample size	3436	334

$$\chi^2 = 33.4, \text{ degrees of freedom} = (r-1)(c-1) = 1 \quad 0.01 > p > 0.001$$

The null hypothesis ("there is no significant relationship between richness and sample size") is rejected at a 5% confidence level. Therefore the relationship is significant.

Cramer's V^2 is used as a measure of the strength of association. It reflects the strength of association relative to the sample size. It is calculated by dividing the chi-square value by the grand total of the data: $V^2 = \frac{\chi^2}{\text{grand total}}$

$V^2 = 0.008$, where zero indicates no relationship. Therefore the relationship is significant, but very weak.

Note on viewing the data collected in this thesis

The data collected for this thesis is presented on the two enclosed 1.44 Mb floppy disks. The disk labelled 'Book 1' contains data from the Beacon Island assemblage in the document 'Book 1' and the disk labelled 'Book 2' contains data from the West Wallabi Island assemblage in the document 'Book 2'. The data was saved to disk in Microsoft Excel version 5.0c (1994) for PC.